

ZURO

1970

THE MAGAZINE OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY
UMTALI BOYS' HIGH SCHOOL

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E D I T O R I A L

"History" - how often does this word evoke an unfavourable response? All too often History is a subject to be avoided at all costs, a mere drudgery. In view of this the object of the Society is to make History a living subject, a subject of use for the future, to show people that the past is inextricably tied up with the present. Thus, it is that the Society makes no apology for joining the ranks of those who would hark back to the past, for we accept as a fundamental that the past is of vital relevance to the present and future.

In this latter regard it is highly unfortunate that History in the classroom has become more a study of chronology rather than a study of people and sociology, for it is surely people (plural and singular) who make history; dates are only there to establish the sequence of events for the student! The study of people and their reactions to certain sets of conditions brings to light patterns of human behavior important for all time and this is the importance of History. Surely, if Hitler had studied the career of Napoleon he would have realised the resilience and stubbornness of the Russian people under siege and would not have attempted his abortive plunge at the heart of Communism, Operation Barbarossa, and there will always be wars as long as both soldier and statesman fail to realise that human behavioral patterns are constant and will always be constant in certain conditions.- albeit Man is a thinking "rational" creature but there are certain instinctive reactions; fear, anger, aggression, pride, that he cannot suppress in lines of crisis, and it is in times of crisis that History is made.

Now, while the History Society makes no claim to have succeeded in providing the answers to the social problems of the world, we do say, or presume to say that in the choice of speakers this year we have found men (and women) who have attempted to and have succeeded in (witness the rising attendance at History Society meetings) imparting their love of the subject to our members. The exuberance of our speakers is evidence that to them anyway History is alive, and History is people - the talks ranged from Archaeology through to Israel today, from Rhodesian history to Cavour and Italy, and in all instances the subject was people NOT dates. If the Historian remembers this latter, History will no longer be dead and a thing of the past, it will be personal, interesting and pertinent. Now, more than

anytime in the past, in this world of bustle and de-personalisation, now, must time be spent on the past, not on dates but on people, social and economic history, we must stop and ask "Why did this man go wrong? Why did this nation collapse?..." And when the answer is found it must be applied to life today - this is History, a guidestone for the future. The History Society is attempting to foster this study of human relationships and our magazine is the embodiment of this desire, for its substance is of men not matter.

D. Gilmour

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HISTORY SOCIETY PAID-UP MEMBERSHIP 1970

D. Gilmour	J. Bekker	R. Vermaak
G. McEwan	M. Petter-Bowyer	J. Milne
H. Clarkson	J. Simleit	I. Milne
B. Davis	C. Poulton	P. Weatherdon
T. Scott	R. McEwan	R. Lister
C. de Villiers	R. Addams	N. Storey
R. Poulton	D. Hughes	L. Kok
G. Cryer	C. Bernhard	P. Kok
W. Vermaak	N. Reynolds	L. Moriarty
S. Cochrane	T. Rudd	J. Smith
F. Winwood	R. Burton	R. Colley
E. Goldsmith	F. Lunderstedt	J. Bernard
D. Futter	I. Harrington- Johnson	J. Winch
P. Walsh	J. Bekker	P. Dennington
M. Stættton	G. Kockott	M. Seward
G. Webster	G. Bleach	P. Lark
		M. Odendaal

CHAIRMAN'S REPORT

<u>CHAIRMAN:</u>	<u>1969/70</u> G. McEwan	<u>1970/71</u> M. Clarkson
<u>SECRETARY:</u>	C. de Villiers/ M. Clarkson	P. Walsh
<u>TREASURER:</u>	T. Scott	D. Futter
<u>COMMITTEE</u> <u>MEMBERS</u> :	D. Gilmour B. Davis	M. Seward P. Dennington.

1970 has seen the society's third year of existence under our new president Mr. Barnes, the society's founder, Mr. Davidge having left us for South Africa at the end of last year. Paid-up membership has greatly increased and we have expanded the scope of our activities. At an extraordinary General Meeting, held on the 6th February, it was decided to extend membership to boys in Form 2B and above and to girls from U.G.H.S. in 'O' Level forms and above. A subcommittee of 6 under the chairmanship of W. Rudd was elected to take charge of our new project on places of historical interest around Umtali. At this meeting a new secretary, M. Clarkson, was elected to replace Cynthia de Villiers, who had resigned, having won a Field Scholarship to America.

The aims of the society, as laid down in the constitution are; first, to foster the study of history beyond the confines of the classroom; and secondly, to encourage the development of local history to reviewing the work of the society over the past year, these aims must be kept foremost in our minds.

An average of three talks has been arranged for each term. These have covered a wide range of topics: from "Early experiences in Umtali" to "The six day Israeli War" and from "A History of Tete" to a talk in Archaeological work in the Umtali area. Two members of the society, D. Gilmour and B. Davis also gave talks, it is hoped that this will be encouraged in the future. Attendance at these meetings has on the whole been very good, a marked improvement over last year.

Two main outings were arranged, to Salisbury to visit the Houses of Parliament and the National Archives, and a three day camp to Zimbabwe Ruins. These can both be regarded as great successes and I feel I must thank Miss Sinclair for accompanying us to Zimbabwe Ruins to act as chaperone for the girls and to help with transport. The success of this trip has prompted us to make plans in another direction this time to the north. The society

hopes to arrange a canoe trip down the Zambezi next year from Tete to the sea - following in the footsteps of early missionaries and trying to recreate the difficulties they must have experienced.

We have shown a series of full length films on historical subjects. It must unfortunately be admitted that some of these were not of great historical value but they aroused a good response throughout the school. In this way they can be considered to have been of some use in stimulating interest in history. I must thank Mr. Wilding and Ian Fisher for making the showing of these films possible.

Through the year, largely thanks to the work of two subcommittee members, Walsh and Seward, the Society has built up a small history museum. This was opened at the fete and aroused considerable interest.

A further new project has been the archeological work the society has carried out at a small fort in Old Umtali. This fort, on Mr. Meikle's farm, was almost unknown and the practical work done there was enjoyed by all. One feels that this type of practical work must be expanded upon in the future.

To stimulate the study of history the society this year decided to award a prize to the best 'O' Level history scholar. This has been awarded to Walsh in C.1 and I would like to congratulate him on behalf of the society.

Finally, I would like to take this opportunity to thank our President, Mr. Barnes, and the committees for all the work they have done to keep the society active this year. I would especially like to mention Clarkson, who, as secretary, has done a very efficient years service; Scott for the enthusiastic way he has dealt with the society's finances; and also Gilmour, under whose editorship, Zuro, has made a definite improvement over those of previous years.

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HISTORY SOCIETY CONSTITUTION

1. Name History Society, hereinafter referred to as 'the Society'.
2. Aims
 - (a) To foster the study of history beyond the confines of the classroom.
 - (b) To encourage the development of local history.
3. Structure
 - (a) Membership will include boys in 2B and above and girls in 'O' Level and above.
 - (b) Subscription. An annual subscription of 50c. will be paid at the beginning of the year. Failure to do so by the end of the first term, will mean forfeiture of membership rights.
 - (c) Control. The direction and control of the Society will be vested in a member of staff of the History Dept. U.B.H.S. and an Executive Committee of Chairman, Secretary, Treasurer and Ordinary member. The committee will meet ONCE a fortnight during term time. The master i/c will have the power of veto which he may use at his discretion.
 - (d) Functions of the Committee.
 - (i) To direct and control the Society.
 - (ii) To plan and effect such measures as deemed necessary to carry out the aims of the Society.
 - (iii) To edit and publish an annual magazine, named "Zuro", covering the Society's activities. The Ordinary Member will hold a special brief for the function.
 - (iv) To prepare and present annually Chairman's and Treasurer's Reports.
 - (v) The functions of the Committee will be carried out jointly, except in the case of the magazine previously referred to, the keeping of all records by the Secretary and the control of all finances by the Treasurer.
 - (e) A subcommittee consisting of a Chairman and six ordinary members, including one from the general committee will be elected each year and will have the following functions:-

- (i) To locate and categorize areas and items of historical interest within an area of some 60 sq. miles around Umtali.
 - (ii) To maintain one room of the school museum for the display and storage of such items as may be collected in (i).
 - (iii) To complete this project on Umtali's history within a period of three years and to publish all the information accumulated and categorized.
- (f) Functions of the Society. The functions of the Society will be defined as all those activities which are designed to carry out the aims. For example - lectures, public talks, seminars and symposiums, film shows, organised visits work-groups.
- (g) Meetings of the Society.
- (i) All meetings of the Society will be by arrangement.
 - (ii) The Annual General Meeting will be held in the first fortnight of the third term.
 - (iii) Extraordinary General Meetings will be called within three days of the presentation of a Petition signed by not less than one-third of the total membership, and stating clearly the purpose of the meeting.

4. Amendments to the Constitution

The Constitution may be amended at the Annual General Meeting or an Extraordinary General Meeting by a two-thirds majority vote.

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TREASURER'S REPORT 1969/70

T. Scott

The Society has had a successful year, financially, with a record number of members, 49, paying their subscriptions.

We have been able to finance the showing of several films with benefit to both historic and aesthetic tastes. The Society also financed a successful four day trip to Zimbabwe Ruins, this cost in the region of \$110; and also a day visit to the Houses of Parliament and National Archives in Salisbury. The Society now has its personal correspondence paper which cost \$6.55.

The above were the main items of expenditure, the total of which is \$221.29. This compared to an income of \$254.59 leaves us with a sum in hand of \$33.30.

INCOME & EXPENDITURE ACCOUNT FOR THE YEAR ENDED 30th
SEPTEMBER 1970

<u>INCOME</u>		<u>EXPENDITURE</u>	
Subs. from Soc. Memb.	24.50	Paper for corres.	1.30
Film - M. Antoinette	20.44	Letter head block	5.25
" - Rasputin	19.14	H. Clarkson for stamps etc.	50.
" - The Agony & the Ecstasy	21.80	Teas	1.20
" - T. Beckett	37.00	Film expenses:	
Donations	1.20	M. Antoinette	10.31
Salisbury trip	17.15	Rasputin	17.99
Zimbabwe Trip	113.36	The Agony & the Ecstasy	18.10
		T. Beckett	27.00
		Expenses:	
		Sby. Trip	17.98
		Zimbabwe Trip	113.36
		Fr. Rea for address to members	8.30
			<u>221.29</u>
		Excess of income over expenditure	<u>33.30</u>
	<u>254.59</u>		<u>254.59</u>

HISTORY SOCIETY SUB-COMMITTEE
REPORT

W. Rudd

Early in 1970 it was decided that a sub-committee consisting of a chairman and six members should be set up. The aims of this group were as follows:-

- (1) To locate and categorize areas, and to collect items, of historical interest within an area of some 60 sq. miles around the town of Umtali, the area being bounded by the Cecil Kop range to the north, the Vumba range to the south and the international boundary to the east.
- (2) Research was to be concentrated on the following topics:- European buildings, African constructions and dwellings (including ruins and paintings), historical monuments and early communications (including evidence of old roads and railways).
- (3) One room of the school museum was to be cleared of non-historical items and adopted for the display of items collected.
- (4) To collect all the research material and photographs used in the writing of the School Jubilee Magazine published by the society in 1969. This was to be displayed in the museum.
- (5) The project was to be completed within a period of three years, the ultimate aim being to publish, in pamphlet form, all the information accumulated.

At the first meeting of the Society in 1970, the following were elected as members of the sub-committee:-

CHAIRMAN: W. Rudd

COMMITTEE MEMBERS: P. Lark, P. Walsh, M. Seward, J. Becker,
P. Dennington, T. Scott.

Research work of this committee was delegated as follows:
European Buildings: P. Dennington
African constructions: J. Becker
Historical Monuments: P. Lark
Museum: P. Walsh and M. Seward
Correspondence & Jubilee Mag.: W. Rudd
Early Communications: T. Scott

The work of the sub-committee during 1970 has been as follows:-

In reasearch the main work has been directed to the ascertaining of the existance of as many areas of interest to the historian as possible.

Corresnondence has been entered into with both the Historical Monuments Commission and the National Archives. This, coupled with the visit to the Archives in the second term, has provided the sub-committee with detailed references to historical items in the area and a detailed index on information contained in the National Archives.

It has not yet been possible to take advantage of the invitation extended by the Archives for a group of members to carry out research, but it is hoped that this may be undertaken next year.

On the practical side, enthusiastic work on the parts of P. Walsh and M. Seward, has completed preparations for the inflood of exhibits which, it is hoped, will appear in the next two years. Walls were re-painted, floors cleaned and extra shelves added. In this regard special thanks must be extended to Mr. Barnes and G. McEwan.

The museum's existing exhibits have been re-arranged and re-catagorized and, along with several donated exhibits, proved to be a crowd drawer at the recent gymnasium fete. In this regard Mr. Bernhard, Mr. Dachs, Mr. Barnes, P. Bekker, R. Beckett and P. Gordon must be thanked for exhibits.

There is still much work to be done over the next two years. The initial research has been completed, but it now remains that the existing information be greatly expanded upon.

It is hoped that a trip to the archives may be arranged early in the first term as well as visits to the areas suggested by the Historical Monuments Commission.

Several new African constructions have been discovered by members of the Society as well as a skeleton at Old Umtali. It is hoped that these discoveries may add interest to the museum display.

With four of the present members returning next year it can be hoped that this project will make great progress in 1971.

The 1971 Project Committee would be grateful if any reader who has knowledge of material which falls within the scope of this project and who is willing to share his knowledge, would get in contact with either Mr. Barnes or the 1971 Project Committee, J. Bekker at the School, so that the member of the Committee dealing with that material may visit the reader at his convenience.

MUSEUM REPORT

P. Walsh and M. Seward

Early in 1970 the History Society took over one room of the museum in order to display local historical items along with research carried out by the sub-committee. The walls were in dire need of repainting and many non historical exhibits had to be cleared out. The floors had to be scrubbed and several shelves added to accommodate the numerous displays. In this regard Mr. Barnes and G. McEwan deserve special thanks.

The second term proved to be equally as active, with preparations for the gymnasium fete and with several donated exhibits (for which thanks must be extended to P. Bekker, R. Beckett, P. Gordon, Mr. Bernad, Mr. Dachs, Mr. Barnes.)

The ultimate display was strikingly impressive and attracted a large number of visitors. A donation box, strategically placed at the entrance, produced \$3.35 towards the museum fund.

Looking to the future, the Society hopes to display items discovered as a result of excavations conducted in the second term at a hilltop fort near Penhalonga; as well as a skeleton uncovered near Old Untali by a member of the Society.

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1. MINUTES OF THE SOCIETY'S MEETING HELD IN THE MAIN STAFFROOM AT U.B.H.S. ON WEDNESDAY 5th NOVEMBER 1969

The meeting commenced at 7.45 p.m. and was well attended. The Chairman welcomed members to the final meeting of year. The Secretary read the minutes covering Mr. Dickinson's talk on Sofala, the first meeting of the new committee and the inter-house quiz. The Chairman then passed on to the chief item of the evening, a talk by Mr. Barnes entitled "The Napoleonic Myth".

The form in which Mr. Barnes presented his speech was to compare Napoleon the Emperor, as time has made him, with Napoleon the man, as his birth and circumstance made him. In order to do this he concentrated, not on the highlights of Napoleon's career, but rather on the pattern of his life both in military and personal fields to see the real man behind the legend which time, the French desire for prestige and Napoleon's own writings made of him. The points which Mr. Barnes brought up in connection with this were very revealing.

It was made clear that none of Napoleon's military strategy was original and even the continental system

was not his own idea. His internal achievements in the spheres of religion, civil reforms and the code Napoleon, were also aspects which had been evolving for several years before Napoleon ascended to power. It was his final drive alone, however, that finally brought them into reality.

Claiming that in order to understand Napoleon's greatness it was necessary to examine the varied facets of this character, Mr. Barnes gave members glimpse of the egotist, the cold-blooded tyrant, the loyal friend and the "family-man" which Napoleon professed to be.

Mr. Barnes said that historians are apt either to be fascinated by Napoleon's personality or repelled by the spectacle of the millions of lives sacrificed to his ambition - but here he pointed out that even Napoleon's enemies admitted that he waged war according to the accepted standards of his age. In conclusion, the speaker said that he thought it legitimate to admire Napoleon's genius, while deploring the ends to which it was put.

After having dispersed some of the mysticism surrounding this great character, and helping the listeners approach a more true interpretation of him, Mr. Barnes joined in the lively discussion aroused by his speech. Tea followed and the meeting adjourned at about 9.15 p.m.

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2. MINUTES OF THE SOCIETY'S MEETING HELD IN THE MAIN STAFF ROOM AT U.B.H.S. ON FRIDAY 6th FEBRUARY 1970

The Chairman opened the meeting at 7.45 p.m. by welcoming the guest speaker, Mr. Hulley and his wife. Attendance was good, about 30 members from both schools being present. He called upon the Secretary to read the minutes of the previous meeting and then announced the business of the evening. He made mention of:-

- (a) proposed film shows on the 17th February (Marie Antoinette) and later in the term (either Rasputin or Beckett)
 - (b) a talk by Mr. Bernhard on Archeology on Friday 27th February.
 - (c) a talk by Mr. Maitin on the 7 Day Israeli-Egyptian war on the 13th March.
- and finally
- (d) He mentioned plans of a trip to Salisbury on March 31st to visit the National Archives, the Houses of Parliament and the Queen Victoria Museum.

Thence followed the main business of the evening, namely, a talk by Mr. Hulley on Early Days in Umtali. Mr. Hulley entitled his speech "Yesterday and Today" and began by giving an account of modern Umtali. He paid tribute to the beautiful playing fields at the school. Turning to the past, he said that facilities of early Umtali were incomparable to those of the present and that it was saddening to think of the early difficulties experienced by the local inhabitants. The population of Umtali was less than one hundred and the children suffered the consequences of limited education and general isolation from civilisation. Mr. Hulley then gave an interesting account of early cricket and tennis matches in the district. He said that it was regrettable that there were no swimming baths, since bilharzia was widespread in the rivers. Transport was a problem, being made difficult by the scattered nature of the town. Horses, ox wagoons, donkeys and to a lesser extent, bicycles were the only forms of transport, although most people walked.

Housing, too, posed a problem. Materials were scarce and the townspeople suffered many discomforts. Iron and wooden buildings were erected and builders were on demand. The Rhodesia Railways were initially administered from Umtali and thus the town developed rapidly. Mr. Hulley concluded by praising the modern chapel at U.B.H.S. and commenting on its significance as a link between the past and present.

Mr. Hulley's speech was well received and several questions were asked.

The next item on the agenda was the election of a new secretary and of a special sub-committee to take charge of a special Historical section of the school museum and to arrange a project on places of historical interest in and around Umtali. The following office bearers were elected:-

SECRETARY: Mr. Clarkson

SUB COMMITTEE: Chairman: Mr. Rudd. Committee members:
Miss P. Dennington, Messrs. Larks,
Walsh, Bekker and Seward.

The Chairman declared the meeting closed at 9.30 and members adjourned to tea.

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3. MINUTES OF THE SOCIETY'S MEETING HELD IN THE MAIN STAFF ROOM AT U.B.H.S. ON FRIDAY 27th February, 1970

The Chairman declared the meeting open at 7.45 p.m and welcomed the guest-speaker, Mr. Bernhard, before calling upon the Secretary to read the minutes of the previous meeting. This was followed by the main business of the evening, namely a talk by Mr. Bernhard entitled

"Archaeology and its Application in Manicaland".

In introducing his subject, Mr. Bernhard said that a hundred years ago Archaeology was a comparatively unknown occupation and that it was only in the present century that it had developed into a highly specialized science. In the Umtali area, however, there had been only limited archaeological study.

A certain Mr. Andrews was the first European to explore the area. Although he excavated several soapstone figurines, which have since been lodged in the British Museum, he employed very primitive methods and destroyed much of the archaeological evidence. The following year in 1905 Professor McIner was engaged by the government to examine all the ruins in the country. He made an accurate assessment of the ages of the various structures and his discoveries were published in a book called "Medieval Rhodesia".

Between 1905 and 1919 there was little progress until Messrs. Summers and Robinson undertook a detailed survey of the area. They discovered several prominent rock structures in the Inyanga area and exposed some highly decorative pottery, of ancient origin. In 1951 this pottery was officially classified as Ziwa Culture (since it had been excavated near the Ziwa Mountain, Inyanga). The various objects were dated back by means of carbon-fourteen tests to the fourth century A.D. and extended to the eleventh century. A more recent culture, that of the Rozwi, is in evidence at Murawaha Hill. The surface layers of Rozwi pottery are underlain by Ziwa structure dating to the ninth century. The Umtali altar was the work of the Rozwi and is the site of many soapstone carvings closely resembling those of Zimbabwe. The oldest pottery in Manicaland and indeed, Rhodesia - is classified as pre-Ziwa and shows evidence of sophistication and the presence of iron. The Makoni and Rusape areas are very uninteresting archaeologically and according to Mr. Bernhard, the early inhabitants were not artists of masonry. Since he had not personally studied the Chipinga and Meisetter areas, the speaker did not feel qualified to give his opinion on their archaeological importance. At the conclusion of his speech, several questions were asked.

The next item on the agenda was a report by Mr. Rudd Chairman of the Special Sub-committee, responsible for carrying out research in local history. He outlined the aims and functions of the sub-committee, and stated that it was hoped to extend the project over a period of three years and ultimately display all exhibits of historical interest in addition to publishing a pamphlet on local history.

Mr. Scott, the Treasurer, then gave an account of the Society's finances and appealed to all members to pay their subscriptions as soon as possible.

The meeting was closed at 8.45 p.m. and members adjourned to tea.

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4. MINUTES OF THE SOCIETY'S MEETING HELD IN THE MAIN STAFF ROOM AT U.B.H.S. ON FRIDAY, 13th MARCH, 1970
(Held in conjunction with the Sixth Form Discussion Group).

The meeting opened at 7.45 p.m. and was well attended by some sixty members. The Chairman welcomed members of the Umtali Boys' and Girls' Sixth Form Discussion Groups and the guest-speaker, Mr. P. Maitin. Following the Secretary's report of the previous meeting, the Chairman announced the main business of the evening, namely a talk on Israel by Mr. Maitin.

Before starting, Mr. Maitin, who had recently returned from Israel, emphasised that his speech would be of general educational value rather than of historical importance. He nevertheless outlined the main events of the country's past mentioning the advents of Judaism, Christianity and Mohammedism and the infiltration of various groups into the country, notably the Phoenicians, Turks and Arabs. Foreign invasion had always been a source of trouble and in the past two thousand years the Jews had been engaged in various struggles to retain their individuality and their country.

Several of the leading towns possess interesting historical backgrounds. Jerusalem, for example, has been continually ravaged by invading forces, the most recent being by the Turks some four hundred years ago. Much biblical evidence can be verified by a study of certain sites in Jerusalem. The present city is a blend of old and new, parts of the city having survived since the time of Christ and consisting primarily of limestone structures, while the newest sector of the city exhibits many fine examples of modern architecture. Ironically, much of Jerusalem is occupied by Arabs.

Haifa, in the north of the country, is in close proximity to the Lebanese border and is thus an important strategical position. Nearby is Acre which is believed to have been the port of call of the Crusaders. The Dead Sea area is about 1200 feet below sea-level and is one of the most barren regions of the entire country. The hot conditions and negligible rainfall, coupled with the constant threat of Arab infiltration (since the

neighbouring Moab mountains form the Jordanese boundary) discourage settlement.

Revolutionary methods have been effectively employed in the development of the desert. Modern agricultural and irrigation schemes have resulted in the production of certain crops previously impossible to grow. Immigrants are being encouraged to settle in the desert areas, and thus serve a dual purpose, firstly, they exploit it agriculturally and secondly, they safeguard against foreign attack.

Superficially, Israel is a peaceful country which is prospering economically. There are, however, strict security measures imposed and a general underlying feeling of tension is forever prevalent. Men are required to do three years of basic military training, commencing at the age of eighteen. Thereafter each man is required for three weeks service per annum until the age of fifty-five. Women, too, undergo military training for two years, their training includes a course in sub-machine gun use.

In conclusion, Mr. Maitin said that he admired the Israeli nation for its ardent patriotism and invincible fighting spirit. In answer to questioning, he said he foresaw a major conflict in the Middle East in the near future. A lively discussion ensued.

Mr. Maitin's speech was well illustrated by colour slides. As there was no further business requiring to be discussed, the Chairman closed the meeting at 9.30 p.m. and members adjourned to tea.

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5. MINUTES OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY'S MEETING HELD IN THE MAIN STAFF ROOM AT U.B.H.S. ON FRIDAY 29th MAY, 1970

The Chairman opened the meeting at 7.30 p.m. and expressed disappointment at the limited number of people present. Following the Secretary's reading of the minutes of the previous meeting, the Chairman called upon the guest-speaker, Father W. Rea, to address the society on the early history of Tete. Father Rea a professor of history at the U.C.R. informed the audience that since the local university was now completely independent, it was hoped that many Rhodesians would attend it.

In introducing his topic, Father Rea stated that the foundation of Sence (some 140 miles from the sea) and Tete (a further 140 miles upriver) was contrary to early Portuguese colonial policy. It was more common to fortify the existing trading stations, rather than develop new areas. These two centres subsequently proved to be of major importance in the context of Portuguese

development of Mozambique, their exploitation can probably best be ascribed to the phrase "Gold and Gospel". The derivation of the name Tete is unknown and the actual date of foundation is also in question, although it was possibly established in the early sixteenth century.

In 1531 the Commandant of Sofala made mention of the Sena area, but it was not until 1560 before there was a positive reference to the name of Tete. In that year a certain Gonzales da Sylvera, a Jesuit priest, undertook a mission up the Zambezi River with the intention of converting the Monomotapa. A fellow priest wrote an account of the expedition, mentioning the trading posts of Sena and Tete. Tete was apparently of some commercial importance, owing its development to its location. Gold was mined in the neighbouring area and Tete, situated on the Zambezi River, was along the route between the land of Monomotapa and the Makaranga to the north. Luanza, a gold mine, to the south west of Tete, was recently excavated.

After 1560, Tete experienced certain difficulties and the Monomotapa secured a stronghold in the area; shortly afterwards da Sylvera was martyred and partially as a result, a powerful Portuguese expedition was sent to Tete to avenge his death, in addition to spread Christianity and to gain control of the gold supply. Francisco de Berreto was in charge of the punitive force and he was accompanied by an adviser and scribe, Montchariz, who described Sena as "a small village of straw huts". Tete was accounted for merely as a "trading post". This was a basically incorrect description, since the Portuguese were more concerned with the acquisition of land than in trading. In return for rendering assistance to the Monomotapa, the Portuguese extorted various concessions and developed the land. De Berreto's expedition was almost entirely obliterated by malaria.

In 1590, another Portuguese priest, dos Santos, presented a more favourable impression of Sena and Tete, mentioning the existence of a fort in the latter settlement. This fortification, constructed of stone and mortar, is of significance because it accounts for the Portuguese survival despite their numerical minority in a hostile area. According to dos Santos the Portuguese were militarily weak, but the Africans were weaker.

Six hundred Christians, including forty Portuguese and a great number of converted Indians and Africans occupied Tete and dos Santos described the village as one of peaceful, modest prosperity. Fruit, crops and vegetables, hitherto unknown in Africa were grown and the local cheese was of high quality. This period of

Tete's history was perhaps its most prosperous and some three hundred years later, Dr. Livingstone was prompted to say "Tete has been the salvation of the Portuguese".

In 1590 however the pattern of peaceful existence altered with the advent of the Zimlas - a tribe from north of Sena. Cannibalistic in nature, this tribe surrounded and attacked the Portuguese settlement at Sena. The Commandant of Tete sent a reinforcement party to alleviate the situation, but this move proved to be in vain, for Sena had already succumbed to the enemy and Tete, now improperly defended and exposed to attack, was easily overcome. Widespread killing resulted from these offensives and the Portuguese were quick to sue for peace. Between the years of 1591 and 1593 a precarious state of peace was maintained; the Portuguese were obliged not to intervene in African tribal affairs and to confine their activities to trading.

By 1597, however, the Portuguese had restored their military power; they successfully devised a method to overcome African fortifications. Forty to fifty men would advance on the African defensive earthworks in a manner similar to the Roman "testudo" system, route their opponents.

At the turn of the century there was an attempt to find silver in the neighbourhood of Chicoo. Mining concessions were acquired from the Monomotapa chief. Records of these concessions are to be found in the archives of Goa. An original document, since been reproduced in a book, gives details of the mineral concessions and bears the date, 1st August, 1607. The Monomotapa repented granting the concession as there was a sudden influx of Europeans into the area and the route between Tete and Chicoo was opened up. Silver resources were limited, however, and little wealth was derived from the mines.

It was at this time that Cabora Bassa (Quebrabasa) Falls were first seen by a European, namely Antonio Mocola. The first series of rapids were apparently about one day's march from Chicoo. Some two hundred and forty years later, David Livingstone arrived in Chicoo, but bypassed the Cabora Bassa rapids to escape paying dues to the local chief. In Tete he was misinformed about the rapids size and splendour and thus failed to make a personal visit to the falls.

The Chief of the Monomotapa was adverse to European prospectors and settlers in the area and desired the expulsion of Portuguese influence from East Africa. He was subsequently replaced by a more tolerant chieftain who renewed the Portuguese mining concession. The years 1629 and 1693 proved to be the period of greatest

Portuguese penetration in present day Rhodesia. Several new Portuguese establishments were opened up, particularly in the modern day Sinoia area and Manicaland. Although Sena and Sofala, the capital at the time and the "Gateway to the Monomotapa", both flourished with the development of the interior. Tete did not experience prosperity. There was a steady decline in numbers and in 1667 mention of Tete's "past wealth and prosperity" was made in the Portuguese records. At that time only forty houses, occupied by Portuguese and halfcastes, remained in the village. In 1624 two hundred Christians had inhabited Tete, as opposed to four hundred a decade earlier. This decline in a period of expansion and development is a puzzling factor, most logically explained by the scattering of population with the opening of new outposts. After 1629 Tete's influence in Portuguese East Africa assumed little of significance.

The early history of the spread of Christianity is described by dos Santos who went to Tete in 1590, although there is a detailed account of the religion of the time, it is evident from dos Santos' account that church facilities were limited. The Jesuits arrived in 1611 and compiled complete records of the numbers of men in Tete, their occupations and other relevant statistics. The Jesuits and later, the Dominicans experienced various difficulties and in 1759 were expelled from Mozambique.

The Portuguese themselves were responsible for their decline. They extorted many concessions from the Monomotapa which aroused African hostility and ultimately war. A sporadic war was fought between 1682 and 1686 in the Manicaland area and the Africans beat the Portuguese by strategy. The Monomotapa seized the opportunity to consolidate on their initial gains and the Portuguese never again recovered their power in Rhodesia.

By 1709, Tete had further declined; the Jesuit church had been burnt and Tete was exposed to hostile incursions. The next fifty years, however, witnessed a temporary revival of Tere economically. Her prosperity was due to renewed gold mining activities in the area and the development of the neighbouring settlement, Zumbo, which proved to be an important link with the coast.

By 1760 Tete's wealth had once more declined. The gold supply had dwindled and the Jesuits were no longer in the area. Portuguese records of 1789 state that Tete was "in a state of neglect and decay".

After 1750 the Portuguese tried to extend their jurisdiction in Mozambique and encouraged settlement. In the years 1830-60 slavery was at its peak and little was done to alleviate it. An attempt to take over Mansangara in the 1850's ultimately succeeded in 1859 and this conquest marked the end of the early Portuguese colonial expansion in East Africa.

After a brief period of questioning which Father Rea answered competently, the Chairman declared the meeting closed at 9.30p.m. and members adjourned to tea.

The minutes of the above meeting were recorded in some detail as an aid to the proposed school tour to Tete and Cabora Bassa. Unfortunately the tour had later to be cancelled but the Society plans a tour to this area in 1971.

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6. MINUTES OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY'S MEETING HELD IN
THE LARGE STAFF ROOM AT U.B.H.S. ON FRIDAY 31st
JULY, 1970

The Chairman opened the meeting at 7.45 p.m. and announced that the meeting would take a somewhat unusual form in that two members of the Upper Sixth would address the society. Prior to this he called upon the secretary to read a precis of the minutes of the previous meeting. This was immediately followed by the first of the speakers, Miss Barbara Davis, who presented a speech on the Franco-Prussian War.

After giving a detailed breakdown of the causes of the war, she outlined the main events of the war. She then gave a graphical description of the conditions which prevailed in Paris during the siege which extended from September 1870 to January, 1871. Food was in such short supply that it was necessary to kill the zoo elephants! Digressing from the war, Miss Davis, turned to Bismarck and the part he played in the unification of Germany. She decried many of his efforts and claimed that unification was a product of chance and circumstance rather than the result of Bismarck's forethought. She credited him with qualities of practicalness and diplomatic skill but reiterated that his part in the unification was limited.

The second speaker, Mr. Gilmour, entitled his speech "The Myth of Italian Unification" and immediately condemned Cavour for his part in the unification. His speech, interspersed with several amusing details, embodied the modern interpretation of the unification, namely that, like the unification of Germany, the creation of a single Italian kingdom was an unpremeditated event.

In the eyes of Mr. Gilmour, Cavour never intended the unification to take place and was more concerned with the expansion of Piedmont. By employing skillful diplomacy, Cavour successfully manipulated events to his own advantage and whenever he was confronted with a crisis, as in 1859, he merely resigned from office, only to be re-elected shortly afterwards. He died in 1861 and thus his contribution towards total unification is somewhat in question. In summarizing the character of Cavour, Mr. Gilmour stated that Cavour was an astute politician with narrow clear-cut aims and that, like Bismarck, approached politics with a practical attitude.

At the conclusion of the two speeches, Mr. Barnes gave an accurate description of the Society's activities as regards the excavations near Old Umtali. He presented a theory as regards the possible habitation of the fort and stated that samples unearthed by the Society's members were being examined and that a report of the excavation was in the process of being compiled.

Before declaring the meeting closed the Chairman drew the attention of the members to various samples on display which were derived from the Franco-Prussian War. These included pieces of stained church glass and wooden splintes. The meeting was closed at 9.00 p.m. and members adjourned to tea.

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7. MINUTES OF THE ANNUAL GENERAL MEETING HELD IN THE
MAIN STAFF ROOM AT U.B.H.S. ON FRIDAY 9th
OCTOBER 1970

The meeting opened at 7.45 p.m. The Chairman welcomed the large audience from the Boys' and Girls' High Schools respectively and extended a special greeting to the guest-speaker, Mrs. Beryl Salt, a radio personality and play-writer, and her husband. After the minutes of the previous meeting had been read and passed, the Chairman announced that the Annual General Meeting would take place and would be following shortly by a speech by Mrs. Salt.

In his report for the year, the Chairman outlined the various activities undertaken by the Society. Several speakers had provided a wide scope of topical subjects; filmshows had been well attended and in addition, outdoor functions had been enthusiastically followed by members. Overall, the year had been very successful and the society had continued to expand. He paid tribute to the outgoing committee and wished the society success in the future.

Mr. Scott, the Treasurer, then presented a report of the Society's expenditure and income for the year. The Society's funds showed a favourable balance and a profit of £32.30 would be carried forward to 1971. In his report, Mr. Rudd, Chairman of the sub-committee presented a detailed account of the aims and achievements of his committee in the year. Although a lot of initial research had been covered in the year, much of the work was still to be done and Mr. Rudd assured the incoming committee of a busy year ahead. His report was followed by the election of a new committee and a sub-committee, for 1970/71. The following were elected to office:

Main Committee:

Chairman: Mr. H. Clarkson
 Secretary: Mr. P. Walsh
 Treasurer: Mr. D. Futter
 Committee
 members: Mr. M. Seward

Sub-committee:

Chairman: Mr. J. Becker
 Committee
 members: Mr. D. Addams, Miss P. Dennington,
 Miss C. Poulton.

Mrs. Salt proved to be a most entertaining speaker and her talk aroused keen interest among members of the audience. She explained the development of her interest in local history and her subsequent interest in play writing. At school she had apparently shown no more than an average aptitude for the subject. She arrived in Rhodesia with a somewhat limited knowledge of the country's past. Her interest was aroused by visits to the Mazoe area and following an initial visit to the Archives where she unearthed a letter written by a certain Folliet Darling three days after the 1896 Alice Mine rebellion, she decided to pursue history as a career. The letter contained a vivid description of the events of the rebellion and provided tangible evidence to the event. In the eyes of Mrs. Salt, this aspect of history assumes a positive reality, unlike mediaeval and ancient history which is frequently obscure, sordidly uninteresting and impersonal. Beryl Salt's interest in history is confined to people and the effect they exercise upon events.

After a successful radio play on the 1896 Rebellion Mrs. Salt decided to expand her talents in the form of a radio serial about Rhodesian history, commencing with the advent of the Pioneer column in 1889. A commercial programme was suggested and following much research, she undertook to rewrite the proposed script.

She decided to write a dramatic history revolving around the personalities. The National Archives provided the source of much of her material and, in particular, the letters of Courtney Selous, Frank Johnson and Colonel Pennefather proved helpful.

Among the problems confronting Mrs. Salt, was the difficulty of adapting the events so that the play had popular appeal while retaining its authenticity. She relied upon the use of sound effects - music, the variation of voices and emotions - to dramatise the play. Because of advertising each episode of the "Rhodesia Story" was restricted to about twenty-four minutes of actual broadcasting time. Apparently the script writing of each episode occupied about five to six hours of her time, while the recording and editing entailed a further two hours work. In all fifty episodes were produced extending from 1889 to 1945. Throughout the play, Mrs. Salt was limited to a cast of four people, who fulfilled the parts of many characters.

She then proceeded to give several amusing anecdotes about Cecil Rhodes, a man of great temperament. After a period of questioning, the Chairman declared the meeting closed and members adjourned to tea at 9.30 p.m.

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TRIP TO SALISBURY

Berry & Becker 3A

On the 31st March, 1970, in the first school term, the U.B.H.S. History Society, organised a trip to places of historical and current interest in Salisbury. Names were taken and finally 22 pupils from Boys and Girls High Schools were chosen.

Thus it was that fifteen pupils departed from Crawford-Palmer Hostels in the school truck driven by Mr. Barnes - at 6 a.m. A further four travelled in a car with T. Scott, Treasurer of the Society, while two more were to be picked up on the way. One was to be met in Salisbury. Although it was bitterly cold at first, it soon warmed up and we had breakfast at Eagles Nest.

After a fairly uneventful journey, we arrived in Salisbury at 10 a.m. and went straight to Prince Edward School where we changed into school uniform. From there we moved on to the Houses of Parliament, where we were kindly met by Mr. Christie and conducted around the building. We sat in the House of Assembly for a time,

while a Mr. Moore explained the working of Parliament such as the function of the Clerks of the Court, Hansard reporters, the Mace and the seating of various parties and the sergoant-at-arms. We were allowed to answer and ask questions afterwards and then we were taken through the building. We saw the old Tapestries which depict the whole history of Rhodesia in pictures, oil paintings of past speakers of parliament and past governors and administrators of Rhodesia.

From the Houses of Parliament we moved away from the City centre to a suburb where we ate our lunches. Because we had arrived late, there was no time to visit the Queen Victoria Museum so after lunch we pressed on to our next port of call: The National Archives.

We found that this visit was a wonderful experience not to be missed. The building, in the shape of a passenger ship was very modern and beautifully built. In the Public Section Rhodesia's whole history is told in Paintings, weapons, jewellery, documents and tools. These relics are very valuable as most of them are unique. After being allowed to wander around the Public Gallery of our own accord, we were taken on a guided tour of the in ards of the Archives. These proved to be a series of huge strong rooms, well protected against fires and thieves, and containing the records (criminal as well) of almost all persons in the Country. We were also shown how the information that the staff receive is sorted and it is surprising how much there really is. Having been through a few more strong rooms we were shown a huge file on the History of U.H.S. the former high school in Umtali. Every single pupil has been listed as well as the various masters. Other interesting material we came upon was the diary of David Livingston which is priceless, Thomas Baines famous paintings and some of Robert Moffats letters which because of the shortage of paper were written crossways and lengthways.

We then passed into the library which contains vitually every known book that mentions Rhodesia in it. It was a huge room and contained hundreds of books. We left with a booklet of Rhodesian History and a great appreciation of what we had seen.

From the Archives we travelled home, stopping only to change at a garage on the outskirts of Salisbury and at Rusape to have dinner at the Balfour Hotel. We arrived back in Umtali at about 8 p.m. after a thoroughly enjoyable and interesting day.

THE HISTORY SOCIETY'S TRIP TO KYLE/
ZIMBABWE

THURSDAY

L. Kok 30

At about 3 o'clock the members met at the school hall. Each person was given a wooden box for his or her personal belongings. We loaded tents, the boxes, food and everything else into the school truck and by 4 o'clock were finished. That night some of the members slept in the school hall and were joined by the others early in the morning at 5.30 a.m. 25 members went on the trip travelling in two vehicles: - the truck driven by Mr. Barnes and the VW by Miss Sinclair.

FRIDAY

It was a cold morning when we set off at a quarter to six. We travelled for about an hour until we stopped for breakfast at Nyanyadzi, an African irrigation settlement about 65 miles from Umtali. After breakfast we continued on our way towards Zimbabwe crossing the Birchenough Bridge on our way. Near Kyle Dame we turned off the main road on to a dirt-track which led across Kyle Dam wall. On this road we had some good views of the lake.

On our arrival at Zimbabwe we divided into groups and set up six tents. Fire wood was collected from a huge pile at the camp and then those on duty prepared lunch. After lunch we played rounders till 2.30 and the whole group went and visited the Karanga Village.
(See "Suro" 1968)

Over here we saw the type of house these people used and inside we saw pots, beads, weapons and various implements used by the people. We also saw their grain bins and an African dressed up as a witchdoctor, playing drums. After this we visited the museum which was very interesting. Over here we saw most of the things that have been found at Zimbabwe. Here were also two models one of the Acropolis and the other of the Great Enclosure. Also there was a model showing how the Africans got stone to Zimbabwe.

After we had seen these two places we went to the Acropolis via the ancient ascent. We wandered through the Acropolis at our own freewill. Over here we saw walls of up to 14ft. thick. On the one wall turrets could be seen. We saw where gold was believed to be smelted and from the balcony a good view could be seen of the surrounding country. There were many passages and enclosures which we explored. We then, returned to camp and supper was made. After supper most of us sat around the camp fire until about 10.15 when we all went to sleep.

SATURDAY

After our breakfast the whole camp set off and at the museum we divided into two groups.

The first group were shown by the curator Mrs. Hodges, a large clump of soil which was being excavated. This dump has been left by John Hall a curator of the Park in 1902. He had been ordered to clear the vegetation within the Great Enclosure doing this rather enthusiastically, clearing off a few feet of soil with the bush. This soil he went through briefly taking out the bigger objects. He dumped the remainder a few hundred yards from the Enclosure. It was on this soil which we sifted, we spent an hour here until the other group "swooped" over, for an hour. In these two hours our party found 250 beads, bits of pottery, copper wire, a few arrow heads, lots of iron, and gold in the form of nuggets and flakes. While one half did this the others went on a radio guided tour of the ruins. We were given tiny earphones and receivers and information was transmitted to us by means of tape recorders. A guide showed us around as we listened. We found out that the great wall around the enclosure is 831ft. long, with a maximum height of 31 ft. At its thickest it is 19' at the base, it is estimated to contain 15,000 tons of stone. We were shown around the various enclosures and taken through dark passages.

After lunch we got into our school uniforms and then visited the Morgenster Mission which is 4 miles from Zimbabwe. This mission was founded by Rev. A.A. Louw in 1891, the year after the Pioneer Column entered Mashonaland.

It is now quite a big place. There are schools at which Africans may learn to be teachers. There is also a homescraft school for girls and a school for the deaf. Ministers can be trained here and there is also a hospital. A printing press prints thousands of books in English and African languages. The Bible was translated into Shona over there and in 1941, to commemorate this event a candle monument was erected. We also saw the "Ginger Rock" on which there is an inscription commemorating the Mission's 50th Anniversary.

After we left the mission we visited the Cheetah Farm. Animals seen included a baby elephant, cheetahs and lions, a crocodile, wild cats, a zebra, a bat-eared fox and a jackal. Also a warthog, a bushpig, a wildebeeste, impala and a stembok. We then returned to camp.

We had supper and then all members went on a midnight tour of the Acropolis while other more nervous types sat by the fire.

SUNDAY

We visited Fort Victoria where we saw the bell tower and then the beautiful Italian church. After getting petrol we then went to the Lake Kyle National Game Reserve. At first as we travelled through the game reserve we saw nothing, but by lunch we had seen 5 giraffe 2 rhino, 2 kudu, an impala and a duiker. We then took the truck to the lake edge and there we waited for the ferry while we had lunch. At about 2 o'clock the ferry came and after a bit of fuss about the weight of the truck we were finally admitted on board. We were the only people on the ferry so that after we gained permission from the pilot of the ferry, we stopped for 5 minutes while 4 members had a swim halfway across the lake. On the other side we parked the truck and then we went onto the wall to look at it more closely. After this we had tea at the tea room above the dam wall. We then visited a camping site where some of us attempted to fish. Back at camp, supper was prepared and then 14 members went to visit the Acropolis, together with a German who was touring Rhodesia and whom we accommodated for the night. We went up to the balcony at the Acropolis and sat here for a long time. After we returned a few of the party talked until half past one in the morning.

MONDAY

We broke camp early, had breakfast and then we set out for Fort Victoria, where we stopped for sweets and petrol. After this we carried on to Umtali with an unarmyfulAt Birchenough Bridge we stopped for lunch and were allowed to stroll around the bridge. After lunch we continued on until about 58 miles from Umtali the V.W. got a puncture. We hailed down another V.W. and soon changed the tyre. We continued and at Sakubva we noticed the left rear tyre of the truck, was slightly flat. However we managed to reach the school, and we unpacked the truck. At 5 o'clock all our parents came to pick us up at the school.

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REPORT ON VISIT TO THE CENTRAL AFRICA HISTORY ASSOCIATION
CONFERENCE

R. Poulton U6

The Central African History Association held its annual conference at the University of Rhodesia during the school holidays from 25th to 27th August., and was attended by Mr. J. Barnes and by three pupils, A. McEwan and R. Pulton from U.B.H.S. and Miss B. Davis from U.G.H.S. The latter attended the lectures only

while Mr. Barnes also attended the discussions concerning the teaching of history.

The first lecture, given by Mr. A.L.P. McAdam, a lecturer at U.C.R., on "President Wilson" proved interesting but it was agreed that at times, Mr. McAdam spoke rather above the heads of the U.G.H.S. and U.B.H.S. pupils, somewhat spoiling an otherwise informative and thought-provoking lecture.

On the afternoon of 25th August, all delegates at the conference met at Fort Mazoe for a guided tour. Although called Fort Mazoe, there is no actual fort as such, but the hill on which the fort was built has two clearly defined trenches, approximately two feet six inches deep, encircling it. The trenches divide the hill into sections of roughly 1/3 each. After the wild climb to the summit of the hill, the delegates were given an extremely interesting account, by Colonel Hickman, of the historic events which occurred in the area during the Mashona Rebellion. From the hill the old Alice Mine, where the people of the area took shelter during the Mashona Rebellion, could be seen. Colonel Hickman also pointed out the site of the recently discovered Routledge and Blakeston telegraph office, from where a telegram, asking for help to be sent to the area, was transmitted.

On the evening of 25th, a public lecture, on "the Zimbabwe Ruins in the light of Recent Research", was given by Mr. P.S. Garlake. It was abundantly clear that Mr. Garlake has a large store of knowledge at his disposal and this was reflected in the way he spoke. Mr. Garlake, during the course of his lecture raised several interesting interpretations of his own as to the origins of Zimbabwe. Mr. Garlake then answered questions from the audience and discussion was lively as was to be expected from a lecture on such a controversial subject.

"An apology for the Middle Ages" by Mr. R.P. Lawton, also a lecturer at the University, once again proved interesting, possibly due to the fact that it was taken from a fresh angle, which added some new light on that particular period.

A lecture on the "National Archives" by Mr. G.E. Burke, and "Rhodesian Bushiography, with a short survey of Rhodesian Publications up to 1890" proved interesting and informative in parts but it found that at times, the lecture was rather disjointed and difficult to follow. On the whole however, the lecture was well delivered and the slides illustrating certain aspects, added extra weight to what was being said.

Perhaps the most interesting and impeccably delivered was by Dr. A.K.H. Weinrich (Sister M. Aquina OP) who spoke on community development. Here too was a lecture which had obviously been derived from a great deal of practical experience and first hand knowledge. Sister Aquina gave an unbiased and fair account of her experiences in the tribal trust lands and it is hoped that she will be speaking to the History Society some time during 1971.

The conference concluded, for the pupils, with a lecture on the National Archives and generally it was agreed that the various lectures provided one with a more sympathetic understanding of the respective topics.

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THE PROPOSED TETE-TO-THE-COAST CANOE TRIP

D. Gilmour UVI

Early in the year, following interest shown in a canoeing venture down the Zambezi, Mr. K. Coates-Palgrave was invited by the Society to give a talk on his experiences on the canoe trip made by members of Prince Edward School from Chirundu to Cabora-Bassa.

Mr. Coates-Palgrave outlined some of the dangers that the Society on its proposed trip, from Tete to the Coast (a retracing of the journeys made by early Portuguese missionaries) would face. These included difficulties in canoeing techniques: how to load canoes; weather conditions likely to be faced, and some of the natural hazards to be encountered.

With these problems in mind the Committee set out to plan our trip. It was decided to approach certain firms and favourable replies were returned prior to the shelving of the trip. There were namely Suters, the fibre-glass and canoe specialists of Gwelo and Illustrated Life Rhodesia who were willing to buy our story.

On the practical side the plan promulgated was for two jeeps to follow the canoes, to carry a relief canoeing crew and supplies, and to set up rendezvous camps at pre-designated spots along the river. These jeeps would then transport the canoes and expedition members back to Umtali from the coast. The 250 mile trip was expected to take in the region of between 12 and 15 days from start to finish.

It was with much regret that this venture had to be postponed due to the lack of support from senior members of the school and also the fact there has been much terrorist activity along the stretch of river intended to be covered during the trip. This, however, is a plan for the future and it is to be hoped that the new Committee for 1970-71 takes up the venture where it was left off.

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A REPORT ON EXCAVATIONS CARRIED OUT BY THE SOCIETY ON RUKWERANYANGA HILL.

G. McEwan

Mr. J. Reeks, an English teacher at U.B.H.S. first came across the small fort at which the Society has been carrying out minor excavations, while out walking. The fort is situated half-way up Rukweranyanga Hill and is constructed around a long, precipitous outcrop of granite. This huge granite outcrop makes the fort almost impenetrable from attack from the south and serves as an admirable camouflage - the fort is not usually spotted until one is almost upon it.

To the west and north-west there are fairly solid walls in fairly good repair. They are approximately eight feet high and four feet wide. To the east and north-east, however, the walls are in a bad state of repair. In general the walling is rough and unskilled. Little trouble had obviously been taken to shape the stones and little attempt was made at coursing. Inside the fortification there is no walling. The natural lie of the land divides the fort into two different levels. Excavation revealed the suggestion of stone flooring on the upper level and a clay surface on the lower.

ARCHEOLOGICAL WORK:

On Friday 11th April, Mr. Barnes and four members of the Society first visited the site. It was very badly overgrown and six pieces of pottery were found on the surface. Only one of these was marked and when later shown to a local archeologist, Mr. Bernhard, it was suggested to be of Warozwi origin.

The Society's next step was to obtain permission from the Historical Monuments Commission and from Mr. Meikle, on whose farm the fort is situated, to carry out excavations. Permission was granted and on 13th June a working group of 13 pupils began to clear the site - a task which took almost all day. Two trenches were begun. The first was inside the fortification on the highest level of the ground. Excavations revealed that

a rocky platform had been constructed. Several fragments of pottery were found, but although we dug to a depth of 40 cms. no evidence of layering was found.

The second trench was dug outside the fortifications, below the granite outcrop. There a skeleton was uncovered, only 3 cms. below the surface.

On Sunday, 14th June the clearing of the site was completed, and a map was made of the fort and the surrounding area. The skeleton was further uncovered, and sieving of the soil revealed a quantity of teeth. The grave aroused considerable interest because the skeleton appeared to have been dismembered before burial.

On Wednesday 20th June Mr. Bernhard went with Mr. Barnes to examine the fort. Mr. Bernhard confirmed that it was typically Manyika and suggested that we

- (i) remove the skeleton and reassemble it in the school museum.
- (ii) sieve the floor of a covered passage on the east side of the fortification in search of beads.

Thus, on Saturday 15th August, another work party went up to the site. The skeleton was removed and the sieving of the soil covering it unfortunately only revealed a small iron "cross". We had hoped for more concrete clues as to the origin of the body. The grave has since been reassembled in the school museum.

On the same day we also cleared the area in front of the entrances to the covered passage, and built up the wall above it to give some impression as to what that fortification must have looked like originally.

ORIGIN

It is estimated that the fort was first assembled towards the end of the end of the 17th century when Changamire and Warozwi first invaded the area. This is indicated by the rather hasty nature of the construction and by the fact that emphasis seems to have been placed on camouflage. Since then it was probably used periodically as a defensive position against slave traders from the coast such as Gungunyana.

RHODESIAN GENESIS

J.C. Barnes

An introduction to the history of Rhodesia prior to the arrival of the European.

Perhaps one should begin by stating that in any record of this kind one is bedevilled by variations in spelling. A.J.B. Hughes and J. van Velson, for example, list twelve variations in the spelling of the word "Lobengula" (including "Ulopengula") and eight for "Mzilikazi". Accepted spellings of Vakaranga appear to include Makaranga, Mokoranga and Makalanga, whilst the Portuguese used Mocaranga. It should perhaps be mentioned here that a difference between the VaKaranga and Vakalanga tribes can be drawn. Father Rea S.J., on a recent visit to Umtali to address the Umtali Boys High School History Society, did mention that he understood the VaKalanga to be that branch of the VaKaranga tribe which had been separated to the west by the Matabele wedge during the last century.

Secondly the prefix "Va" (Wa, Ma) in the Shona language is usually used to denote the plural. Hence a Karanga is a member of the VaKaranga tribe, and so with the VaRoziwi (Wa Rozwi), the WaRemba, even the Manica (VaNyka). Many writers tend to drop the prefix for the sake of simplicity but I have preserved it in the following paper, not least because it enhances the natural beauty of some of these African names.

C.K. Cooke, writing on behalf of the Historical Monuments Commission in the pamphlet "Digging up the Past" suggests that "Man has probably been living in Rhodesia for over a million years, but we have found little evidence yet to prove that he was here more than 60,000 years ago". The story of mankind almost certainly begins with small bands of food gatherers who possessed no permanent habitation but made a precarious living by collecting roots and berries and by slaying such animals as they were able to catch. "But at some stage in this development these primitive people achieved the greatest advance ever made in the history of human endeavour".(2) They began to fashion tools according to a set and regular pattern, hence the STONE AGE.

Archaeologists divide the Early Stone Age into several periods, beginning with a little known PEBBLE CULTURE, which was gradually succeeded by the CHELLES ACHEUL culture. Gradually primaeval craftsmen improved their techniques and implements related to the SANGOAN cultures contain hand-axes cleavers and scrapers of various kinds, although these tools, roughly worked, are seldom found but remain buried well below the surface.

It was probably during the transition from early to middle stages of Stone Age development that Boskoid Man (Skeletal remains, found at Boskop in the Transvaal) and Homo Rhodesiensis ("Broken Hill Man") roamed this country - that is, when Rhodesia experienced more rainfall than it does today, when Stone Age hunters penetrated wider areas of grassland and when there developed what has become known as the RHODESIAN STILL BAY cultures. Roving bands hunted with spears furnished with stone points, cave-dwellers fashioned small scrapers, backed blades and pierces and some of them even learned the difficult art of boring a hole through stone.

In the ensuing drier period a new culture, known as the MAGOSIAN, developed which centred on perennial streams where animals would come to water.

The later Stone Age is marked by further advances in the technique of working stone and by the hafting of small, highly finished stone blades into wood or bone. Arrows were lighter thus giving a greater range, they had barbed points and were dipped in a poison which was harmless when swallowed but fatal when injected into the blood stream. But the SOUTHERN RHODESIAN WILTON CULTURE was not limited to new weapons. A splendid rock art was developed which can still be seen, for example, at Diana's Vow, Rusape and which has been referred to as "Bushman Painting" because the BUSHMAN are the most recent survivors of the Later Stone Age.

There was no BRONZE AGE in Rhodesia as there was in Europe. Several writers have set upon this to explain why the African should not have developed the wheel, but the logic behind this argument is questionable and the theory is not in popular use today.

The Stone Age people had not learned to herd cattle or raise crops, they lived from "hunt to mouth". But at some time towards the end of the Stone Age, probably about 2,000 years ago, the nomads of the veld suddenly encountered strangers who lived in a very different fashion. Bushman painters have recorded this invasion, and in Ruchero Cave, Mtoko, there is a picture of two men and two women, who lead a cow between them, "perhaps one of the most important scenes ever to have been executed in this country". (3)

This "Volkerwonderung" of the early IRON AGE people is marked by the introduction first of a characteristic kind of "stamped ware" pottery, that is pottery adorned with channelled patterns as well as the impressions of square-toothed stampes - and secondly of clay models of the human figures called figurines,

representing a cult of fertility worship. These people probably introduced cattle and the cultivation of small grains, although sheep may have been introduced by earlier nomadic bands of pastoralists, the HOTTENTOTS, on their way to the Cape.

The earlier Iron Age people seem to have lived on friendly terms with the Late Stone Age hunters and no doubt interbred with them. R. Summers has put forward an interesting possible explanation of this peaceful coexistence (4). He argues that the Iron Age people came from the Zambezi via the Mazoe and Ruenya Rivers, that is tsetse fly areas. Consequently they would, at first, have had no cattle meaning that there was no immediate competition for grazing grounds. As the numbers of Iron Age settlements increased however, and cattle increased, the Late Stone Age hunters were driven from their hunting grounds because their water supplies were being used by stock and their wild fruit trees cut down during preparation for the planting of agricultural lands.

Finds belonging to the Iron age, beside pottery, include ornaments made from ostrich egg or snail shell, glass beads, some bronze tools, and ornaments and cross shaped ingots. It was at this time that the extraction of metal, especially gold, became an important industry and iron slag and furnace remains, as well as hut foundations and burials of the later period, can also be found. Some Iron Age people also painted in the caves and shelters but their work in no way compares with that of their Stone Age predecessors - it is usually crude and non-representational.

The most striking of Rhodesian Iron Age sites are the ruined stone buildings such as those of the Great Zimbabwe, Khami, Naletale and Dhlō Dhlō, as well as the Inyanga pit structures, terraces and water furrows. From the buildings have come imported wares from China and other eastern countries, usually dated to the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries.

The final phases are just before the arrival of the European when rough stone wall enclosures were built as a protection against the raiding Matabele imbis.

In following an archaeological bias however, we have overreached ourselves - it is necessary to turn back to the immigrant people represented by Bushman artists. To categorise the early arrivals is to become involved in controversy. According to Summers the "very name (of these people) is forgotten and ought not even to be labelled "Bantu" (5) but Mr. F.C. Bernhard, who found the skeletal remains at the Ziwa site, has no doubt that they are Bantu.

Almost all we know about these people is based on relics contained in pits and rough terraces in Inyanga from whence comes the beautiful ZIWA pottery (1*) Their peaceful relationship with the Bushman has been explained, but they also had trade connections with the east coast and Arab traders. As there is no gold or copper deposits in Inyanga the article of trade was probably ivory. The culture was not extensive and whether it was ended by drought, by the exhaustion of the soil or by some other means, it is impossible as yet to say.

The expiration of the ZIWA Culture coincided with increased BANTU MIGRATIONS to Rhodesia. The term "Bantu" is "a linguistic term without any racial bases". (6) These immigrants differed from the Ziwa in that they were cattle keepers, they had a different religion, a complicated social structure, a system of chieftainship and they were great builders.

It has been suggested (7) that the Bantu were basically from Asia, although they had long been settled in Egypt and the Sudan. Why should they have moved south? - perhaps because of an increase in numbers, perhaps because especially after the death of Mohammed (632 AD) the Arabs spread by force the new religion of Islam. They are a cross between Hamite (light skinned) Negro (black skinned) and Bushman, which of course explains the difference in appearance, and their path is marked not only by pottery, figurines and gold mining activities but also by the earliest dry stone constructions, built primarily for defence against later invading waves of Bantu. It is interesting to note that parts of the foundation walls of the "Acropolis" at the Great Zimbabwe date back to the eleventh century.

Early immigrants included the forerunner of the SOTHO groups. Among the Sotho tribe there is evidence that the ancestors of the BAFKENG and BAROLONG crossed the Zambesi during the eleventh century and remained in Mashonaland for over 200 years. It has been suggested that they were associated with the Zimbabwe Culture and developed the gold trade with Sofala. When the early Shona invasion crossed the Zambesi (about 1450) the Sotho retreated either to the Northern Transvaal or South West to Bechuanaland, where they mingled with the Bushmen and Hottentots.

A thriving Bantu society therefore occupied Mashonaland between the eleventh and fifteenth centuries. The Bushmen were driven west to the rocky outcrops and eventually to the fringes of Lake Ngami where the swamps

(1*) Mr. Bernhard has recently found on Murahwa's Hill some pottery similar in design and age to that of the Ziwa pottery from Inyanga.

teemed with wild game.

The Bantu migratory waves however had not ceased. The biggest and possibly the most important group arrived several hundred years after the turn of the first millenium. This was the VAKARANGA group, sometimes recognised as the SHONA invasion. The term "Shona" is in fact a poor one. It is generally regarded as a "derogatory name whose exact meaning is doubtful; it was apparently applied by the Ndebele (Matabele) conquerors (in the nineteenth century) to the indigenous population" but historians have used it "to cover all Bantu people who speak dialects officially recognised as Shona". (8)

The Shona people soon divided into different sections as in times of war or drought the head of the family would lead his relatives in new directions. This explains why the main Shona tribes today - for example the Vakorekore, Va Nda, VaZezuru, VaManyika and VaKaranga (perhaps from "Kuranga" meaning to "exert authority") - have similar customs but slightly different languages although they can understand each other's speech.

A series of Arab and Portuguese documents has meant that our knowledge of the VAKARANGA people is more detailed than that of their predecessors. An Arab settlement and trade in gold has been established at Sofala by the year AD 956 and if one can sidetrack for a minute, an interesting feature is the Arab influence still to be seen in WAREMBA people. The frequent marriages between Arabs and Bantu women has resulted not only in the WaRemba retaining customs similar to those of the Arabs, but these people still retain Arab names - for example Hasani, Savyidi and Sherefi.

The Portuguese captured Sofala in 1505 and their documents refer to the interior as "MOCARANGA" (VaKaranga) or "the land of the Monamatapa". The Monamatapa was the chief of the VaKaranga and he lived in a "Simbao" called "Mbire" on the Mxengesi River north of present-day Salisbury. The word "Simbao" is obviously the derivation of "Zimbabwe" but what of its meaning?

De Barros, writing in the mid-sixteenth century (9) records that "the natives of this country call these edifices Symbaoe, which according to their language signifies court and they say that, being royal property, all the king's dwellings have this name". What is immediately noticeable is the omission of any reference to stone or stone work. This has prompted some to suggest that the word Zimbao, when used by the Portuguese, means simply

the chief's kraal whether it be constructed of stone or simply a village of thatched huts. D.P. Abrahams (10) however has argued that the 'court' aspect is merely incidental - what is important is the connection with stone. The word "Zimbabwe" he suggests, meaning "stone place", refers to any kopje that has been fortified for purposes of defence. F.W.T. Posselt (11) has traced the derivation of the word to dzimba (houses) and mabgwe (stones). Run the two together and one gets "houses of stone". But when asked to put "houses of stone" into his own tongue a Mashona does not simply join two nouns. Charles Bullock (12) has returned to the Portuguese interpretation but his explanation of the derivation is interesting. Noting that the word has been used for the headquarters of a Native Commissioner when the official was regarded by the natives as having taken over the powers of the Paramount Chief, he suggests that both the suffix and the prefix of the word magnify the meaning of the root "mba" hence we get "The Great House" - the House of the Chiefs (alive or dead). This is comparable with the suffix and prefix in names of mountains, for example Umvukwe, or Zishabano (Europeanised to Shabani).

What of Great Zimbabwe itself, near Fort Victoria? Roger Summers (13) rightly points out that it is 850 years since the first buildings were erected on the site and it is impossible to have any great degree of certainty about the identity of the builders. Archaeological and anthropological evidence suggests that the ancestors of the Shona but especially the VaKaranga are likely to have had a large hand in beginning the work. As has been detailed the VaKaranga were responsible for much of the actual gold mining in this country and were therefore sufficiently advanced technically to have tackled stone buildings. The WaRozwi, successors to the VaKaranga, may have followed and improved the building technique. The Warozwi besides being fine organisers, were also great "magicians" and were thus capable of providing a sufficiently powerful religious stimulus for the erection of Zimbabwe's most important buildings.

Recent archaeological research by Mr. P.S. Garlake supports the above. He argues that Zimbabwe was built not for defence but primarily to enhance the prestige of a wide-ruling group. Only later did it come to have a religious significance. Furthermore, he argues that the absence from the Zimbabwe area of any oriental ceramics which can be dated post-fifteenth century suggests that Great Zimbabwe started to decline as early as the fifteenth century.

At this point, in the light of what has been said above and not forgetting the title of the book most recently published on Zimbabwe (14) an interesting angle emerges. The WaRemba (Lemba, BeLemba) have recently

claimed that their forefathers built Zimbabwe, and, says Summers, their claim deserves attention on the grounds of technical ability. Did they work under the guidance of the WaRozwi, who were themselves small in numbers but who had a special talent for welding together small groups? If there is any significant Arab influence at Zimbabwe, was it transmitted via the WaRamba people?

The VaKaranga group was not the last of the Bantu migrations. In the middle of the sixteenth century Mashonaland was visited by a wandering military group, the FAGA, who originated in the highlands of Eritrea. The more ferocious ZIMBA, a century later, were to roam almost unchecked south of the lower Zambesi. Although the VaKaranga managed to survive these depredations, they were finally to succumb to a third wave, and one which seems to have originated with the ranks of the Shona themselves, that of the WAROZWI (BaRozwi, MuRozwi).

The task of the WaRozwi, was made easy by the various schisms within the Shona kingdom. In 1565, for example, the Monomotapa, Mokeambo, was attacked by a rebel chief Chikanga. Both were killed in the fighting but their successors inherited the feud and the tribe was split into two parts, Chikanga's extending over present-day Manicaland. Further disputes in 1570 resulted in two other divisions - a group under Kiteve spread inland from Sofala to the hills of Chipinga and Sitanda grouped his tribe around the lower Sabi River.

To the west, in the region of the Motonos and beyond were a people, early Bantu in origin, referred to by the Shona as ABUTWA. "Twa" is a name used by the Bantu meaning "foreigners", "not of our race". Gold was not mined here, the people rather being pastoralists.

How did the WaRowzi alter this picture? In 1677 Chief Changamire of the WaNyai people, said to have been the son of the Monomotapa and a slave woman, and a veritable Shaka of his day, attacked three Portuguese forts and destroyed them. Hence the name WaRozwi, meaning "destroyers". The surrounding tribes were conquered and in 1693, Tete, Sena and later Macequece were captured. The Monomotapa himself was defeated and Changamire took over the kingdom, calling himself "Mambo", a title which persists among the VaKorekere, VaZezuru, Manyika, VaNdau (Melsetter) and WaRozwi today. The Mambo exercised his power by playing a vital role in the selection of all subordinate chiefs, irrespective of tribes, and he conferred on them a head covering which acted as a staff of office. This prerogative is still maintained by certain WaRozwi representatives over various tribes.

A closer look at the name Changamire is interesting. The Chief's original name was simply Changa but, perhaps owing to Arab influence, he took the title of Changamire which was inherited thereafter by his successors. (In fact most Shona chiefs adopt a hereditary title on succession: for example Makoni of the Ungwe, Mutasa of the Manyika). In time "Changamire" became the laudatory response to a pronouncement by a ruler, meaning "let the chief live", or, as we might say "Your Majesty". Thus it was several Native Commissioners heard it as a polite assent given to any of their dictums by old and polite Natives.

A.J. Wills (15) has suggested that it was possibly because of the WaRozwi attacks that the inhabitants of Inyanga were driven to take refuge in the highlands, where they maintained a precarious existence for two generations or more. Partly for shelter and partly for defence they constructed stone ramparts around pits dug into the ground whilst the kraals for their livestock were also made of stone. Eventually they were able to return to the lower and more fertile slopes although their neighbours did not permit them at once to inhabit the level and more hospitable veld. Summers (16) has suggested the eighteenth century as the most probable time for the construction of the Inyanga terraces and the 1950/51 Expedition to the Inyanga Ruins declared that "it was a shortage of building material rather than a desire for permanence that led the Inyanga People to depart from the more usually Bantu materials - wood and mud - for building their huts and walls".

The WaRozwi did not remain isolated but mingled with their subject communities. They made use of the stone forts in the south and kept them in repair - Great Zimbabwe, for example, was occupied until the early nineteenth century, at which time it was abandoned in favour of the structure at Dhlo Dhlo. In some places at Great Zimbabwe new stone enclosures were built but the work was roughly accomplished and was never of the former quality.

The signs of an organised industrial and agricultural community withered and gold production declined. An eighteenth century account (17) states that they were much devoted to their chief but that "they pass their whole lives in indolence and spoliation, hold agriculture and commerce in contempt, and consider themselves superior to other races. Plunder is their sole objective..."

After 150 years the WaRozwi hegemony was terminated when the "destroyers" themselves fell prey to those Bantu who were migrating north from Natal, away from the turmoil

of Shaka's wars. The most important of these were the SHANGAANS under Soshangana, the NGUNI (Angoni) under Zwangendaba and the MATABELE (Ndebele) led by Mzilikazi.

The reasons for the "mfecani" or Zulu "Explosion" whereby there was a general exodus of tribes away from Zululand, are complex and need not detain us here. What is important is that in 1818 Shaka attacked Zwide, rival chief of the Ndwandwe clan, and as a result three of Zwide's indunas were to take sections of his tribe and lead them north. Soshangana for example, nephew of Zwide, gathered a few warriors of the Nxumalo clan and led them north between the Lebombo Mountains and the sea. They crossed the Limpopo and raided the Tonga tribes with the result that, after capturing slaves and young men, Soshangana had a big following. He gave his people the name "Abakwa Gaza", "People of Gaza", because Gaza was the name of an early chief of the Nxumalo clan. This in turn was used later by the Europeans to denote the area "Gazaland" centred on Chipinga.

Shaka sent an impi after Soshangan which, although it did not reach him, caused him to move further north to the Sabi River and then in-land where, by attacks on the MaNyika tribes, his name became known and feared by the Shona speaking Bantu. Fighting in the Zulu manner with big shields and short stabbing assegais, the SHANGAANS, as they had become known, even attacked the Portuguese forts at Inhambane, Sofala and Sena, which were held virtually until the death of Soshangana in 1856.

Another of Zwide's subjects to flee before Shaka was Zwangendaba, who had been Zwide's chief induna and head of the Kumalo Clan. With a handful of warriors he moved north along the Lebombo Mountains before crossing into the land of the Swazi, Ntungwa and Sotho. Here he came into conflict with Mzilikazi and he was forced to turn back towards the country of the Tongas. But this was still too near the impis of Shaka for him to remain in safety and so he crossed the Limpopo and turned in land to the country of the VaKaranga and WaRozwi. He settled temporarily near Rusape and his Swazi impi attacked the Mambo of the WaRozwi - Rupengo - in his zimbabwe at Dhlo Dhlo, driving him to Thabas a Mambo (Taba zi ka Mambo) where they caught and killed him. Rupengo's younger brother, Mutinima, escaped and led the remaining WaRozwi south-west to Khami. He had hardly settled there before he heard of the coming of Mzilikazi and the Matabele, with the result that, in 1839, he moved to the Bikita district. Either he or his son took the name Jiri, which is still used.

Still Zwangendaba had not found the country he wanted. In 1835 he led his people across the Zambesi (by which time they were known as the A'NGONI) to the shores of Lake Tanganyika from where they have since split up and moved both north and back south.

The third induna to be affected by Shaka's attack on Zwide was Mzilikazi, chief of the Kumalo clan. When the Ndwandwe tribe was broken, Mzilikazi moved to live near Shaka's kraal, Bulawayo, in Zululand. His popularity however, aroused jealousy and when, in 1822, he failed to hand over all the cattle he had captured in a raid he was compelled to hurriedly leave. He chose the westward route over the Drakensburg where he was attacked by Zulu impi. Moving north he went through the Bechuana and BeSuto Tribes until, crossing the Vaal River, he reached the district of the Marico River where he built his kraal Mosega. It was here that he was visited by "Mtshete" (Dr. Robert Moffat) who told him of good land to the north, and was attacked by the Boers (1837) and by an impi sent by Shaka's successor, Dingaan. Mzilikazi decided to move north once again away from both Boer and Zulu. He divided his tribe into two groups:- the first, the Mnyama - Makanda ("Black heads" so called from the black plumes of their head dress) which included Mzilikazi's eldest son Nkulumane, moved north-east until they came in 1838 to the Matopos Hills, where they waited for Mzilikazi to join them. 1838 is normally considered to be the foundation date of the MATABELE nation, the word Matabele coming from "N'debele" referring to the large Zulu-type shield carried by these warriors. Mzilikazi himself was with the Mhlope (white) group, following a path further to the west. They went into the Kalahari desert from which they emerged sometime later after tremendous hardships. They came to where the Gwaai and Khami rivers join and raided Chief Zwanki (Wanki).

Meanwhile the Mnyama-Makando group, tired of waiting for Mzilikazi, elected his son Nkulumane as their chief (Nkuluman was named after Kuruman, Moffat's mission station in Bechuanaland, in honour of Moffat.) Before he could be formally elected however, Mzilikazi found his way back to his people (1840). The indunas who had chosen the new chief were executed but the fate of Nkulumane is unknown - it is possible that he was killed as well and Mzilikazi, to cover up the murder, spread the rumour that his son had been sent to Zululand for reasons of safety.

The Matabele found it easy to make themselves masters of the new country - the WaRozwi had already been defeated by Zwangendaba and the A'ngoni and, together with the VaKaranga tribes, they lived in constant fear, often hiding in secret places among the rocky

kopjes to escape the Matabele. Those that were captured or vanguished became the servants of the Matabele.

Mzilikazi built two kraals, the first at Inyati, the second at Mhlahlandela and it was at the latter that he died in 1868. Lobengula, son of Mzilikazi via a lesser Swazi wife, was reluctant to accept the crown lest Nkulumane should suddenly return and Lobengula suffer a similar fate as had happened to the indunas in 1840. Thus it was that the Matabele were ruled for two years by their chief induna, Mncumbata, whilst every effort was made to find Nkulumane. After his chieftainship had been formally recognised in 1870 Lobengula built a new kraal "GuBulawayo", which was to be the nucleus of the European town after 1893 and which is now recognised as "Old Bulawayo".

Lobengula's reign saw the influx of Europeans into Rhodesia. The two races lived in a tolerable state of co-existence until the first trial of strength in 1893- skirmishes between Matabele and Mashona, the raiding of cattle and an unsuccessful "indaba" between Jameson and the Matabele indunas resulted in Major Forbes' march on Bulawayo. Lobengula, on his flight north, realised that the supreme power of the Matabele was ended and after Allan Wilson's last stand on the banks of the Shangani River he sent his warriors back to their homes with orders to make peace. He himself, riding a horse as he suffered badly from dropsy and gout, wearily made his way north to Mlindi where, in January 1894, he died.

No successor was recognised. Lobengula left six sons, three of whom were educated in the Cape at Rhodes' expense. One of these, Njube, was generally regarded as Lobengula's heir although no formal recognition was made. He died and left two sons, Rhodes and Albert - in the Umtali Boys' High School library there is a copy of Hillaire Belloc's "Waterloo" with a neat inscription inside the cover to the effect that the book first belonged to "Albert Lobengula".

In March 1896 the Matabele burst into rebellion and almost 200 Europeans were slaughtered. Four months later the Mashona rebelled and laagers at Salisbury and Umtali followed those at Bulawayo, Gwelo, Mangwe and Belingwe. The quelling of the rebellion in the south was the last occasion on which the Matabele were treated as a single political unit. Since that time they have been divided up for administrative purposes into a number of districts and have been administered merely as a part of the African population of the state of Rhodesia.

The tribes of Rhodesia today number more than one hundred, of whom the great majority are commonly called MaShona, mainly to distinguish them from the Matabele and the smaller groups of Sotho and Bushmen. The sample census of 1848, which may be considered representative, gave the total number of indigenous Africans in Rhodesia as 1,638,900, of which the Matabele probably numbered between 300,000 and 400,000; that is 18-24%.

The 1970 constitution for the republic of Rhodesia is interesting in the light of the above figures and history. The fact that percentages can be ignored in providing for equal representation of Mashona and Matabele on the Senate is merely a further illustration of the effectiveness with which Mzilikasi and his numerical minority stamped their supremacy over the inhabitants of the country we call Rhodesia.

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- (1) Hilda Kuper, A.J.B. Hughes, J. van Veben: "The Shona & Ndebele of Southern Rhodesia": Ethnographic Survey of Africa; Part 1, (1955) p.118
- (2) L.H. Gann, "A History of Southern Rhodesia" (1965) p.3
- (3) Ibid, p. 5.
- (4) R. Summers, "Inyanga" (1958) p. 312.
- (5) Ibid p. 311
- (6) Ibid p 311
- (7) W.T. Miller, "A History of Rhodesia", (1965) p.17
- (8) Kuper, Hughes and van Veben, op.cit. p.9
- (9) Quoted in Theal's Records, Vo. VI, p. 199.
- (10) D.P. Abrahams, "The Early Political History of the Kingdoms of Mwene Mutapa", date of publication unknown.
- (11) F.W.T. Possett, as quoted in an addendum by Bullock (op.cit) p.14.
- (12) C. Bullock, "The Mashona and the Matabele" (1950) Chp.II
- (13) R. Summers, "Zimbabwe, A Rhodesian Mystery" (1965) pp 74-76
- (14) T. Muller "The Arab Builders of Zimbabwe" (1970)
- (15) A.J. Wills, "An Introduction to the History of Central Africa" (1964) p.28
- (16) R. Summers "Inyanga" (op. cit)
- (17) J.N. Andrade "Report of Trade Conditions" (1789).

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TIME CHART - Majority of dates are obviously estimates.

I R O N A G E	300	Settlement on Murahwa's Hill	Ziwa Settlement began	Evidence of settlement at Zimbabwe		
	400					
	500					
	600					
	700					
	800					
	900				956 Arabs at Sofala	
	1000	BANTU MIGRATIONS INCREASE				
	1100			Foundations of Acropolis		
	1200	SoTHO				
1300						
1400						
1500	Faga	Zimba			1505 Portuguese capture Tete, Sena, Sofala.	
1600						
1677	Changamire's W revolt			Mambo at Zimbabwe		
1700						
1800						
1830	Angoni, Shangaans	Matabele				
1890	Pioneer Column					

VAKARANGA

TRANSITIONAL PERIOD

INYANGA RUIN PERIOD

BASIC BUILDING COMPLETED

THE ASSASSINATION OF PRESIDENT KENNEDY

Members of Form 11A

THE DEATH OF A PRESIDENT (P. Dunn)

Kennedy arrived in Dallas, Texas, at 11.40 am on November 22nd, 1963. He was accompanied by Vice-President L.B. Johnson and both their wives. Shortly after their arrival they took their places in the motorcade and set out for the Trade Mart, where the President was due to speak at 12.30. President and Mrs. Kennedy sat in the rear seat of a special Lincoln convertible while Governor and Mrs. Connally were seated in the centre seat. Vice-President and Mrs. Johnson followed in another car.

Crowds slowed down the motorcade and at 12.30 it had only reached the Dealey Plaza in the town centre. As the cars turned into Elm Street, a shot rang out, apparently from the direction of the Texas School Book Depository Building. The President clutched his throat and Gov. Connally screamed. A second shot hit the President and he collapsed.

Mrs. Kennedy climbed onto the back of the car but Secret Service Agent Hill pushed her back in and shielded the dying President from any further shot. The car proceeded at top speed to Parkland Hospital, four miles away.

The President was rushed into the emergency room and died at 1 p.m. Following evidence given by eye-witnesses the police searched a grassy knoll on the north side of Elm Street, but finding no evidence of an assassin, turned their attention to the Book Depository Building, where Oswald's gun was located.

THE CRUCIAL HOUR (J. Swanepoel)

12.30 p.m. Kennedy was shot. One minute later Oswald was stopped by a police officer as he attempted to leave the Book Depository Building, but after the caretaker had identified him as an employee, he was allowed to leave.

12.35 p.m. According to the Warren Commission, Oswald left the building.

12.40 p.m. Oswald entered a bus 7 blocks away from the building.

12.45 p.m. The bus was halted in a traffic jam and Oswald got off.

12.45 p.m. Deputy Sheriff Craig saw Oswald enter a station-wagon IN FRONT OF THE DEPOSITORY BUILDING (given in testimony to Warren Commission).

12.45 p.m. Police given description of Oswald in connection with the assassination.

12.50 p.m. Warren Commission states Oswald entered taxi.

1 p.m. Oswald arrives at his lodgings in Oak Cliff Area.

2.05 p.m. Oswald's housekeeper swears a police car halted in front of the house, blew its horn twice, and drove on.

1.10 p.m. Police Officer Tippet, who had been instructed by head-quarters to go to the Oak Cliff area while all other cars were called to the Dealey Plaza, made two UNSUCCESSFUL attempts to contact police head-quarters on his radio.

1.15 p.m. Police head-quarters informed Tippet had been shot by a passing citizen calling on Tippet's car-radio.

1.45 p.m. Police radio announces "Informed a suspect went into Texas Theatre".

1.50 p.m. Oswald arrested at Texas Theatre.

THE WARREN COMMISSION (P. Weatherdon)

The Commission was appointed by President Johnson to investigate the assassination. It consisted of Earl Warren (Chairman) R. Russell, J. Sherman Cooper, T. Tale Boggs, G.R. Ford, A.W. Dulles, J.J. McClay and J.L. Rankin. They received their information from two main sources - the F.B.I. reports and testaments from 552 citizens. The final report was released on September 27th, 1964 and consisted of 912 pages.

The report concluded:

- (i) Lee Harvey Oswald, acting ALONE killed the President.
- (ii) Jack Ruby, also Acting ALONE, killed Oswald two days later.
- (iii) Oswald fired 3 shots - one struck the president in the back of the neck, exited from his throat, and passed through Gov. Connally; a second bullet shattered the back of the president's head, and the third missed completely.

The report was accepted by all American newspapers and it was not until 1966 that it was seriously challenged.

THE CONFUSION OF THE MEDICAL REPORTS (N. Le Roux)

The greatest challenge to the Warren Commission Report comes from the conflicting medical reports. Three doctors conducted the examination of President Kennedy and reported two wounds - one in the back of the head, and the other in the neck. From this report the conclusion was drawn that two bullets hit the President, although no bullet fragment of any reasonable size was located in the body.

Dr. Humes (one of the three doctors involved), however, has given evidence that during the later stages of the autopsy he located a THIRD bullet hole two inches below the shoulder blades, in the President's back. He probed the opening with his finger and found it no longer than his finger - BUT THERE WAS NO BULLET INSIDE, AND NO EXIT HOLE. A bullet was found by an F.B.I. agent on a stretcher in the hospital, BUT IT IS NOT KNOWN IF THIS WAS THE STRETCHER USED FOR THE PRESIDENT. The holes in the President's

THE REMARKABLE PATH OF THE PRISTINE BULLET ACCORDING TO THE WARREN COMMISSION.

shirt confirm he was hit in the back as well as in the neck.

UNANSWERED QUESTIONS (J. Horrocks)

1. WHO SHOT KENNEDY? According to army records Oswald was a poor shot and in the reconstruction of the shooting even the best riflemen, who had much better conditions than Oswald in which to fire, missed the target.
2. HOW DID OSWALD GET THE GUN INTO THE BUILDING? The Warren Commission said he dismantled it and wrapped it in paper, passing it off as his lunch when questioned. The smallest the rifle can be reduced to is, however, over three feet in length.
3. HOW DID THE POLICE GET OSWALD'S DESCRIPTION TO BROADCAST AT 12.45 p.m? The only known source for the description is the officer who stopped Oswald as he was leaving the Depository Building, but he only reported it to head-quarters at 1 p.m.
4. WHY WAS TIPPET UNABLE TO GET HEAD-QUARTERS ON THE RADIO? According to the Commission Oswald shot Tippet after being stopped by him. No explanation has been offered for Tippet's inability to get through to head-quarters.
5. WHY WAS TIPPET SENT TO THE OAK CLIFF AREA? Every other police car was sent to the Dealey Plaza.
6. WHERE DID THE POLICE CAR, WHICH STOPPED IN FRONT OF OSWALD'S COME FROM? No explanation has been offered.
7. DID OSWALD KILL TIPPET? Oswald's housekeeper swears Oswald was wearing a dark jacket when he left the house, but a light jacket was found by an "UNKNOWN" policeman near the body of Tippet. No explanation of the jacket has been offered.
8. HOW DID RUBY GET CLOSE ENOUGH TO KILL OSWALD? Several hundred policemen were charged with guarding Oswald but Ruby walked by them all with a pistol and killed Oswald.
9. WHY DID THE TEXAS POLICE REFUSE TO MOVE RUBY WHEN HE OFFERED TO GIVE IMPORTANT INFORMATION OF THE DEATH OF KENNEDY, Ruby refused to give this information to the Texas police but offered it to any other state police force. His request was refused.
10. COULD ONE BULLET HAVE PASSED THROUGH BOTH KENNEDY AND CONNALLY? The bullet produced by the Commission would have to have followed a remarkable path (see illustration), AND the bullet had NO TRACES OF BLOOD ON IT and was undamaged.

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ADOLF HITLER

Keith Jacobs (5B)

Throughout history there have been evil men who have become powerful for various reasons: Attila the Hun, Ivan the Terrible, and many others. Yet not one of these semi-legendary figures has even approached the barbarous scale of Adolf Hitler's atrocities. If only to seek a reason for six million deaths we should try to understand him as a person.

POLITICAL OUTLOOK

In its early years the Nazi party was as much a socialist as a nationalist organisation. Its appeal was largely to the workers and out of work soldiers. Yet essentially Hitler did not care very much for the lower classes with whom he had been forced to live cheek by jowl in Vienna. Nevertheless, he realised that he could derive much support from them and thus it was only after he had achieved virtual total control of Germany that he openly dropped the socialist element in his party. On the "Night of the Long Knives" (June, 30th, 1934) Hitler, Himmler and Goering moved to the left wing of the party. The S.A. (sturmabteilung, of brownshirts) traditionally a socialistic group and its leader Ernst Roehm, were liquidated. Hitler after this never gave the people of Germany a say in government. Samps, like the Volkswagen Company, were handed to them but the workers really were no more than one more source of power to be harnessed for Hitler's personal advancement.

Although Hitler never really wanted world war. He realised that Germany must be ready to wage one. Under the direction of men like Speer, Schacht and Todt Germany was geared to a war economy. Economically this relieved the stress on millions of jobless men and put Germany on a superficially sound footing. But in the long run the German economy would collapse if not given a war on which to use its vast quantities of war material. Hitler had conceived of an idea, propounded by early German romantics like Schlegel and philosophers like Nietzsche and Treitsche, that the whole state was a single body. This body was subordinated to one head (Hitler of course) and as the Aryan body was immeasurably superior to any other, it must gear its whole self to asserting itself. This Hitler did. Industry was to be made self sufficient and able to supply itself with synthetic (ersatz) raw materials, rather than foreign imports. German finished products were to be sold for raw materials. Weapons were to be exported.

Under Schacht, firms like Drupp's Iron and Steel works turned out tanks, planes and guns, even though each of these had been banned by the Versailles agreement.

Despite vast increases in production figures Germany was not however at her peak of production until 1943.

It was for just such large scale governmental backing that industrialists like Krupp and Kirdof had given financial backing to the early Nazi party. Indeed, it may even be said that without it Hitler may never have been anything more than a provincial loudmouth in prison. In this connection Rohm and Goering were well known in pre-war industrial circles. In fact Goering's main contribution to early Nazidom was his close association, through social contacts, with the industrial magnates.

In return for this aid Hitler gave German industry protective tariffs and cheap labour, namely convicts.

In "Mein Kampf" Hitler says of the Jew: "He is a parasite, a sponger, who spreads over wider and wider areas accordingly as some favourable area attracts him". Hitler further stresses that he only realised how evil the Jews were when he met one in Vienna. He gradually developed a fierce, pathological hatred of the Jews. That he should have done so for no other reason than his own unreasoning prejudice is typical of the man.

Hitler like Mussolini, thought himself a well-read intellectual. In actual fact his reading was limited to such authors as Kant, Hegel and Nietzsche, of this reading he absorbed little of worth and merely twisted and bent it to fit his own personal beliefs.

The belief in the natural superiority of the German race was not Hitler's prerogative. Early nineteenth century poets in Germany, fired by Prussia's stand against Napoleon, turned to medieval romanticism. In the past these men found a belief in their inherent biological superiority as a race. At first merely an outpouring of patriotism in the contemporary vein of the romantics, serious scientists took up the phenomenon and transformed it into what they believed to be a scientific fact. The belief was that the Aryans, a militant culture in early India, had somehow transmuted their qualities to the modern German. Hence the Nordic race - tall, blonde, strong and intelligent - were "Herrenvolk" whilst sub-humans like the Jews and Russians were "untermenschen". Because of their superiority the Aryans were entitled to subjugate these races and turn them into mere slaves. It is interesting to note that of the Nazi leaders only Heydrich could be said to fit the idea. Rohm was a fat homosexual, Rosenberg an ugly little Russian, Goering a gross man, Hess was so dark that he was nicknamed "The Egyptian", Goebbels was club footed and Himmler was dark and ugly.

Hitler used these "facts" as weapons to regiment German society. One could not have "relations" with Jews, the racial purity was to be maintained. These opinions found expression in the Nuremberg Decree of 1934 - the legal code was bent more than once to incorporate Hitler's personal animosities.

Hitlers' attitude to racial theory had its roots background. He was born in a part of the Austro-Hungarian Empire more German than Austrian. An imaginary chip on his shoulder developed because of his rejection by the Old Austrian artistic and architectural circles in Vienna. Jostled about in old Vienna, which was a perfect hotch-potch of races, Hitler became inordinately proud of his Germanic background.

In practical terms Hitler meant to make inroads into the "Bolshevistic, Asiatic, sub-human "East". Poland and Russia were to yield "Lebensraum" (living space) for the rapidly expanding German population. Jews were to be completely irradiated - they were to be burnt, gassed, shot, hung, beaten, poisoned and starved into non-existence. The other sub-humans were to become baggage animals, lower than horses.

What is most ghastly about the "final solution" was not its brutality but its sheer scale and the coldly analytical way in which it was handled. Complaints came from H.Q. in Berlin, not about the number of dead or the brutality in the camp, but: "Why has 1263-2's head not been shaved?", "Where is 96237's wooden leg?" after the war the allied courts merely had to read the S.S.'s own meticulous records to condemn them.

Hitler's association with the army was an odd one. In the early years Hitler placed much reliance on the "Frei-Korps" for his thugs and even some of his leaders. It is also a fact that the post First World War army in Bavaria clandestinely supplied the Nazis with money. The attitude of the army was that it had been betrayed by the "soft" politicians after the war. The army conceived of the dream of re-establishing the power of the old general staff. This amelioration was only possible in a strong authoritarian state. They saw in Hitler the puppet they could use to bring this state about. Essentially the army was conservative and it was shocked by the spectre of world socialism. Hence, Hitler's rabid anti-Boloshevism found favour in their eyes.

Hitler, however, did not wish to have to rely on the army. He hated the old, snobbish, general staff which would not accent him. Consequently he developed organisations of a semi-military nature, such as the S.A. and S.S., which would eventually usurp the position of the regular army. This is clearly revealed by his rapid advancement of S.S. officers in the war and his marked preference for S.S. army divisions.

Once in power Hitler began to form elite S.S. divisions to be under his personal and not O.K.W. (Oberkommando des Heeres) command. The army swore their oaths to him personally, but opposition in the army was developing. Hitler realised he could not drop the army. Thus to kill two birds with one stone he agreed to destroy the S.A. and drop the socialist element in the party. In return the army chiefs agreed to back him up in his aggressive foreign policy.

Yet the old school of German officers, men like Von Beck, von Rundstedt and Fritsch, would not or could not like him personally. Hitler's dabblings in military matters were usually disastrous and, away from his presence, men did not regard him particularly well. It was a different story when they were confronted by him - his eyes, it is commonly agreed, had an hypnotic effect on people. They could not resist his power to attract.

After securing the armed forces Hitler proceeded to act against its hierarchy. Plans to eliminate Hitler had been prepared in the event of a single reverse to his expansionist policy, but this policy did not have any reversal and so the wind was taken out of the revolutionary sails.

In 1938, Hitler dismissed generals Blomberg and Fritsch (the latter on a trumped-up unproven charge of homosexuality) and replaced these men of great moral stature with Jodl and Keitel, two weak, pliable puppets. This set Hitler's tone for the army, but luckily for Germany he had not had time to place all his favourites when the war began. By 1944, however, mediocre soldiers, like Schorner, and Reichnau were field marshals in charge of vital fronts. Ultimately Hitler ruined his won army by misguided policies. After all he was only a corporal.

His constant fear of an army rebellion led to the formation of elite Nazi units like the 12th S.S. "Hitler Jugend" and the "Death's Head" Division. These were fine troops but it meant that by the time recruits had filtered through the Luftwaffe, panzer and paratroops, only low grade men reached the ordinary line units.

A.J.P. Taylor has labelled Hitler's foreign policy as being a completely opportunist one. Others have suggested that Hitler had a firm fixed plan for the expansion of Germany. The truth in all probability lies somewhere between these assertions. Undoubtedly Hitler used favourable circumstances and the blunder of his enemies to further his policies. His seizure of the Rhineland in 1936 succeeded only because of the chaos caused by an election in Paris. The French, had they decided to, could probably have marched direct to Berlin, so weak was the German army at that stage.

In 1938 Hitler called Schusnigg, the Austrian Chancellor to Berchtesgaden. In a violent, screaming diatribe against him Hitler completely overawed the man. The result was that when Seyss-Inguart assumed power in Austria and invited the Germans to invade, Schusnigg was incapable of action. Once again Hitler had profited from the inaction of his enemies.

In 1939, Hitler entered the Sudeterland, an area of Czechoslovakia that had a predominantly German population. This move was regarded as being a fair one by world opinion and a conference was called to decide on some settlement. In Munich Hitler became a quiet, conscientious worker for peace. Neville Chamberlain was impressed and felt assured that "Her Hitler" wanted to take over Czechoslovakia purely for the actual safety of his people. Hitler, with his protestations of peace and vociferous "this is the last" assurances, duped Chamberlain. It must be said that the unfortunate Chamberlain was not the only one to be duped by Hitler. Too much has been heaped on his shoulders. He was wrong, but it was only a tiny group of men like Churchill who saw the light. Most people agreed with Chamberlain dreading a repetition of the Great War and did not criticise him until after the war had actually begun. He then became the national scapegoat.

Indeed Hitler's success went to his not-so-brilliant head and he was genuinely surprised when the "sensible" English went to war over Poland.

Hitler's attitude to Russia was an anomaly. His stated aim was the complete destruction of Bolshevism. Hitler had a fervent, unreasoning abhorrence of Communism. It was based on.... nothing. Nothing, that is, but his own perverted pettish hate. In fact Russia was to provide "Lebensraum" for the Aryan master race - a sort of form-aim-colony-cum-source of raw materials for the German people. It is indeed strange therefore, that Hitler's advances to Stalin for some sort of alliance were well received. The results of visits to Moscow by Libbentrop and to Berlin by Molotov was a non-aggression pact between the two powers. This agreement, signed in 1939, was a division of Europe into spheres of influence. Russia was to be dominant factor in Eastern Europe whilst Germany was the source in the west. The result was Russia's seizure of the Baltic states and her invasion of Finland. It meant further that when Germany invaded Poland on 1st September, 1939, Russia did little but seize her pound of flesh from Poland.

This uneasy alliance lasted until the 22nd June, 1941, when, after trouble over Russian encroachment on oil-rich Rumania, Stukas dived and tanks clattered into Russia. Once "the west had been won" Hitler made his greatest blunder and fulfilled his greatest ambition by attaching Marxism.

In France, after the death of Clemenceau and Poincare, interest in repressing Germany waned and internal problems took the limelight. Consequently the only really anti-German act of France after the seizure of the Ruhr in 1923 was the alliance with the eastern nations of Czechoslovakia and Poland. The former they sacrificed, over the latter they went to war.

This weak foreign policy of France was a vital factor in the advance of war. Had France been less war weary she might have extinguished Nazi power quite easily on several occasions. Her inaction gave a vast boost to Hitler's inflated egomania and gave him a false assessment of his own relative capacity to overawe the world.

Hitler's feelings toward Britain appear to have been a mixture of envy and contempt. He believed that Germany and Britain could co-exist peacefully. Apparently Hitler was influenced by an Oxford Union debate - the motion "I would fight for king and country" was defeated. That he should have believed this to be a serious, widespread point of view reveals his own lack of understanding of the British people. These very students flew, and flew well, against the Luftwaffe later on. In effect the British were willing to go to war once the true nature of Hitler's character and plans were revealed. He should have realised that Britain could not disassociate herself from the continent and that she was sensitive to any radical change in the status quo.

It is a common misconception that Hitler held Mussolini in contempt. In fact Hitler really admired, even envied, Mussolini. Indeed it was Hitler, not Mussolini, who was the newcomer to the Fascist scene.

One of Hitler's greatest defects was the manner in which he imprinted his personal beliefs on major aspects of his foreign policy. His violent petty prejudices became an important factor in determining the future of most of Europe.

CHARACTER

Hitler's character was much influenced by his early life. His small minded father and flamboyant, rather unbalanced, mother did not try to thwart his every childish whim. When his father died in 1903 all trace of control vanished. Hitler was a complete failure at school. He was "insolent and contanterous" and only did well in History. Significantly only his history master was praised by him later. He conceived an ambition to be an artist and so he went to Vienna, unashamedly living off his mother's meagre funds.

The Vienna Academy of Arts refused him on the grounds that his painting was not good enough. He cried "victimisation" and tried to become an architect. As he had no academic qualifications he could not be accepted, but his extreme vanity led him to believe he was a great architect and even as late as 1944 he was drawing up plans for the world's greatest art gallery, in Linz.

After his rejections and the death of his mother in 1908 Hitler had to live a hard life, labouring and painting picture postcards. Living close to the lower classes he developed an abhorance of them. He who argued and talked about his beliefs to anybody who would listen. It was here that he developed his ranting style of speech that was later so effective.

The war came as a relief to him. He moved to Munich and joined a Bavarian regiment. He managed to submerge himself in it. He appears to have been a good enough soldier, earning an iron cross and ending the war as a lance-corporal. In the final stages of the war Hitler was temporarily blinded by gas. When the terms of the Versailles agreement were revealed he was in a hospital in Danzig, and he immediately ranted against the "Criminal betrayal of the army by the politicians".

Hitler drifted down to Munich and became an army political observer. Early in 1920 he was ordered to report on the meeting of a small right wing group - the group that was to become the National Socialist Party. Hitler was angered by the speech of one old man and jumped up and began speaking himself. After his talk he was offered a place in the party hierarchy, and soon he was the accepted leader. By disciplining his small party and attracting industrialist capital, Hitler soon made the party something of note in Bavaria. He organised the group into a tight military organisation, issuing attractive uniforms and adopting evocative slogans, chants and emblems. What was more important perhaps, he built up a band of ex-soldier thugs who protected Nazi rallies and disrupted those of their opponents. Brutal, gangster methods terrorised people and brought them "into line". Psychological effects like the infectious "Sieg Heil" chant and the darkening of the auditorium except for Hitler himself soon won many people to the Nazi party. Far at the time Hitler impressed the hitherto unspoken, somehow disgraceful thoughts of most Germans and convinced them that their thoughts were clean, healthy and good. He has been described at one hall meeting as beginning to read a speech. The speech was a bad one. Hitler cast his script away and talked spontaneously. His voice, dropping from hysterical screechings to almost inaudible basses, completely captured his audience.

His oratory was not reasoned but purely spontaneous. In his speeches he said very little of worth but the way he said it was completely in tune with the psychological state of mind of his audience. His emotional appeal was stupendous.

There can no longer be any doubt that Hitler was a chronic megalomaniac. But it is not enough to merely state the fact: we must seek its cause. There has developed of late a school of "psychological history." Eminent doctors and psychiatrists have linked their knowledge to that of history. Thus Napoleon's bad friend, Kaiser Wilhelm II's shrunken arm and George III's childhood have all become major factors in determining the reasons for the actions of these men. Something similar may be applied to Hitler.

Perhaps as the result of his blindness by gas in the Great War, Hitler developed Parkinson's Disease. This was a nervous complaint which caused twitches of various kinds. It also caused a general feeling of melancholy and debilitations, particularly later on, when he lived almost solely underground. Hitler developed just such fits. Even in the midst of a conference he suddenly turned pale and his left leg began to twitch convulsively. Such attacks were followed by typical "no surrender" diatribes.

In fact by 1945 Hitler was a wreck of a man. He rarely spoke, seldom listened to reports and would frequently break into storming rages. His eyes, subjected to the artificial lighting of his bunkers, were so weak that they had to be shielded with a shade. Indeed it appears amazing that in this state he could still exert his authority on the men around him.

The end Hitler chose to put to his life reflected his emotional make-up. Hitler's favourite composer was Wagner. Given this the rest falls into place. He had a mania for the legendary folk songs of Germany and Scandinavia, for Siegfried and the Nibelungen, and Odin and his Valkyries. Some Nazi leaders, notably Himmler carried Germany's mediaeval history to ridiculous lengths - even to the revival of the Teutonic order of Knights in an old, renovated castle.

Thus it was on April 30th, 1945, that Adolf Hitler shot himself, and, like every self respecting Viking warrior, he had his body burnt on a funeral pyre. It may be noted that he used up several gallons of petrol that might have better been used in sending some people to the west.

"THE MEN FROM THE HILLS"A History of Manicaland Rugby

J. Winch

The virtual non-existence of Manicaland rugby is a severe blow to the Eastern Districts, not only because it is a disappointment that an area of this size cannot raise a four team league. The main blow is to Manicaland's proud history of rugby success which does not deserve such a fate, particularly when one considers the tremendous reputation it had established for itself twenty years ago. Let us slip back to the Salisbury Sports Club in 1948, "The Men from the Hills smote the Men from the Plureship and thigh", is an apt description of the thrashing the Manicas, led by Schalk de Villiers, inflicted on the Mashonas before a stunned and silent crowd of some 5,000. On that day Manicaland became a force to be reckoned with in Rhodesian rugby and what magnificent rugby they played. Newspaper write-ups quoted Viljoen and Brink as hitting the home centres "so hard that they began to pack up" whilst Koch and Slabbert "jumped as if they had springs in their heels" The names Koch (Bubbles), Viljoen and Slabbert were well-known as all had represented the great Western Province side in the past years. Koch was to play for South Africa the following year. Rarely has one province had the captain and vice-captain of Rhodesia as Manicaland did that year, respectively Schalk de Villiers and Daantjie Viljoen.

It is little wonder that so much was expected of Manicaland in 1949, and the year started off well with a fine fourteen points win over the famous Cape Town "Villagers". By this time Salty du Rand and Ryk van Schoor had joined Inyazura - men who were later to become all-time rugby "greats". Manicaland overran all the other Provinces whilst their players were to play a prominent part in Rhodesia's outstanding show against the All Blacks. The Allblacks who had had victories over the strong Western Province and Transvaal fifteens to their credit, crumbled to the Rhodesians at Bulawayo. Manicaland's Koos Brink had an excellent game and scored one try through a brilliant piece of uncanny anticipation. Another local player John Morkel led this Rhodesian side in its first moments in rugby history, and played a stirring game himself. Another Manicaland representative Ryk van Schoor had a workmenlike game but he was too give a superb performance in the drawn match in Salisbury. On this occasion, All Black's skippers, Fred Allen, when asked about van Schoor's tackling, said ruefully, "The tornado, why I am black and blue." Van Schoor was regarded with Springbok colours, as was Du Rand.

Manicaland again had the captain and vice-captain of the Rhodesian side in 1950, Morkel and van Schoor holding the positions this time. The highlight of this season was the victory a Manicaland - Mashonaland side had over the Junior Springboks. Of the touring side ten were to represent South African in the next couple of years. John Morkel's side won by 26 points to 14 - Morkel, Slabbert and Du Rand were conspicuous for their hard work in the tight and the loose whilst Van Schoor electrified the crowd with some beautiful runs. On one occasion Van Schoor was pulled

inches from the line (Halkett following up scored) but made up for it, scoring two beautiful tries by cutting through the smallest of gaps like greased lightning. Another local star Slabbert scored fourteen points with his boot ensuring that all the Manicaland players shone in the combined side.

Incredible as it may seem, the rugby fanatical town of Umtali was given a Currie Cup game between Rhodesia and Natal in 1951. True to the occasion the Manicaland players starred in a resounding 19-5 win to the home side. The performances of Ryk van Schoor and Salty du Rand guaranteed them re-selection for South Africa. Du Rand scored twice and Van Schoor, who had the best run of the day, scored once. Mention must also be made of Kevin Curran, who still represents Manicaland in cricket, for it was his scheming, safe pair of hands, quickness off the mark, fine sense of anticipation and well-judged kicking that had so much to do with the sound performance of the Rhodesian back-line and overall, the side's excellent display. It was not surprising that Curran was rewarded with a Springbok trial but unfortunately was not selected for the South African side to tour the British Isles, although du Rand and Van Schoor were.

Van Schoor left Manicaland after the tour but du Rand stayed on and became captain of Rhodesia. Salty however was also to leave at the end of the season and an era passed by. Over a period of five years three Springboks had played Manicaland rugby. Du Rand and Van Schoor in particular had brought glory and honour to both club and country. On the 1951-52 British Isles tour they were the only two players from one club to play in all five tests and the match against the Barbarians. The one scored the first try of the tour and the other the second and similarly the one scored the first try of the tests and the other second.

But instead of deteriorating Manicaland rugby flourished in another era, if not more magnificent than the first, then just as successful. A clean sweep was again made over the other provinces in 1953. Wickers de Kock, the present Member of Parliament for Rusape, made his debut for Manicaland and for Rhodesia that season. Evergreen Kevin Curran and John Kitcat again had good seasons whilst Daantjie van der Spuy was to grace the Manicaland rugby field for the next ten years. Never will one forget Van der Spuy playing without boots in the final game against Mashonaland and scoring two tries.

Piet de Klerk made his debut in 1954 and was to represent Manicaland for the next twelve years, being capped for Rhodesia on almost fifty occasions during those years. Unfortunately, this was the year when Manicaland went down at long last to Mashonaland (13-9) but it was that "Makoni hoodoo" which cost them the game. Four times John Kitcat attempted penalties and each one

hit the upright and rebounded the wrong way. Nevertheless Kitcat was to have some outstanding games for Rhodesia that season, Van der Spuy taking over the national captaincy and de Klerk making his debut. The following year Van der Spuy was vice-captain of the Junior Springboks whilst John Kitcat was noted by the British Lions as the best full-back they came across on tour. Wickers de Kock, who succeeded van der Spuy as Rhodesian captain, was strongly expected to lead the Junior Springboks in the Argentine a couple of years later but this did not come about.

The second colourful era of Manicaland rugby passed by quickly and the town had to wait for no other than Marthinus Jacobus Martin to revitalise the local rugby scene for a brief period in the 1960's. For two years he made Inyazura the top club in Rhodesia whilst he spearheaded Manicaland's success in regaining the Russell and Du Plessis Cups and the Black and White Trophy. But even this did not match the golden years of the late 1940's and early 1950's. Occasionally memories are often brought back; Piet de Klerk's great climax to his career by leading Odzi to the Club Championship of Rhodesia in 1964, is but one; but it will be many years before the personalities and the thrilling rugby produced in Manicaland's heyday are equalled again in Rhodesia.

It is also doubtful if one will again see the star-studded Salisbury and Bulawayo sides pounded into the ground by a bunch of farmers led by a couple of "Biltong Boys" as they were known - "Salty" du Rand and Schalk de Villiers. The crash-tackling of Ryk van Schoor has carved a niche in Rugby history whilst names like Brink, Viljoen, Slabbert, Kitcat, Van der Spuy, de Kock, Curran Kock and de Clerk will always be proudly remembered in local rugby circles. It was through these players, and others, that Manicaland rugby reached its glorious heights and undoubted leadership of Rhodesian rugby between 1948 and 1958.

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THE SUFFRAGETTE MOVEMENT

P. Ellis CII

In 1928, the House of Lords gave its approval to a measure with the unexciting name of the Equal Franchise Bill by which women were entitled to vote on the same terms as men. The bill was passed quietly, without speeches, almost apologetically, in the manner of someone repairing a rather obvious oversight. Thus ended, undramatically, a struggle which had lasted just over sixty years and which had been waged with the most relentless bitterness on both sides.

The struggle to obtain equal rights for women can be said to have begun in 1792 with the publication of Mary Woolstonecraft's book, "Vindication of the Rights of Women", but as a political issue and something more than just a vague desire, it can be conveniently dated from 1867 when the philosopher John Stuart Mill brought in a Women's Suffrage amendment to the Reform Bill. This amendment was rejected. During the next twenty years, agitation was kept up by the various branches of the National Society for Women's Suffrage which sprang up all over the country under the leadership of Mrs. Henry Fawcett. These societies, though very active, were intent on achieving their ambition by constitutional means and enlisted the sympathy of a great many politicians. Certain minor gains were made but the real goal, the vote for women, was as far off as ever due to the fierce hostility of the men in power. The quiet approach of Mrs. Fawcett's suffragists seemed to have failed. New tactics were found in the suffragettes of Mrs. Pankhurst.

Mrs. Pankhurst had been concerned with the Manchester suffragist movement from 1889 and by 1901 she was on the committee. She was impatient at the lack of progress and so she decided that shock tactics might be more effective. In this way the Women's Social and Political Union was formed and later became the Militant Suffrage Society. They were to begin with a very small group, not much bigger than the Pankhurst family. There was Mrs. Pankhurst with her three daughters, Christabel, Sylvia and Adela, a teacher - Theresa Billington and about twenty other women. Soon a new and valuable recruit arrived to join them, Annie Kenney, a mill girl whose courage and stubbornness and devotion remind one of Joan of Arc. The W.S.P.U. began operations in Manchester and right from the start they got down to work. They bought no luxuries so that all money could go to their work. They disciplined themselves strictly and worked unrelentingly to put their viewpoint before the public. Then in 1905, at a huge meeting of the Liberal Party, there occurred an incident which put the Suffragettes on the offensive. Annie Kenney, waving a small white banner emblazoned "Votes for Women", asked the speaker, Sir Edward Grey, if the Liberal Party would give women the vote. The question was ignored and she shouted the question again. She was joined by Christabel and a riot ensued, ending when the two women were ejected from the hall by the stewards and the police. The following morning Annie and Christabel were brought up for trial "for assaulting the police". Fines were imposed on them with the option of going to gaol for seven days. They chose prison, to save money, and a packed meeting welcomed them when they were released. Annie Kenney was sacked from her job at the mill and became virtually a member of the Pankhurst family. From now on, she was a full-time worker for the

During the general election of 1906, the Manchester Suffragettes were perpetually in action and grew steadily in numbers. Yet their leaders were not satisfied with the results. They decided to switch the scene of operations to the "enemy headquarters" - London. Annie Kenney was sent on ahead as organiser and so well did she play her part that on the day when the new parliament assembled, 350 women marched to Cayton Hall where they held a protest meeting. Soon the Suffragette Movement had developed into a tremendous force. Its membership included women, as well as men, from all classes of society, while its increase in numbers made it no longer possible for its opponents to dismiss it as some crazy idea thought up by a few women. The Suffragettes were in fact helped by the stupidity and brutality of those in authority. Time after time these women were sent to prison where they were treated with less consideration than a common criminal. They were locked up in narrow cells with almost no ventilation and they were not allowed to exercise at the normally appointed time. When they protested they were put in solitary confinement or strapped up in leather jackets. Occasionally, they were handcuffed for a whole day and their hands were only freed for meals. When they went on hunger strike, they were forcibly fed. As a result of this, a great many people who had previously not cared about votes for women, changed their attitudes when they learned of such indignities.

Meanwhile, the struggle increased fiercely. The Suffragettes invaded the House of Commons and were thrown out. They travelled all over the country, whenever there was a by-election, and made life miserable for the candidate who did not support their cause. At one of these elections, in Devon at the beginning of 1908, Mrs. Pankhurst was severely beaten up by a crowd of roughs, only one of whom was punished with a fine of five shillings. At another meeting, a young woman who resented the candidate's remarks about the Suffragettes, signified her displeasure by turning up at all his subsequent meetings armed with a large and very loud muffin bell. On 21st June, 1908 the largest gathering (except in present days) ever witnessed in Hyde Park was organised by the women who were anxiously and unnecessarily as it happened, supervised by a total of over 600 policemen. The government, however, took no notice and refused to meet a delegation from the various organisations that had assembled. This merely had the effect of making the women more determined than ever. Twenty-one of them attempted to rush the House of Commons. A Suffragette in a dirigible balloon drifted over the building in what was probably the first leaflet raid. Three members of the Women's Freedom League went into the Ladies' Gallery of the House, chained themselves to the grille with padlocks and kept shouting "Votes for Women". A locksmith had to be fetched before they could

be removed. On one occasion, a vehicle made up to represent a "Black Maria" appeared in the streets. Women in prison dress descended from it and began chalking the streets and distributing hand bills to passers-by. In Glasgow, a girl climbed on to the roof of St. Andrew's Hall and lay there in a downpour, interrupting a meeting inside by calling down through a skylight. One Member of Parliament had just begun his speech when he was interrupted by Suffragette slogans which came, apparently, from an organ in the hall. Two women had hidden in it all night. Ladders had to be fetched to get them out and the meeting was abandoned.

At last it began to look as though the government was about to yield. In 1909, the new Parliament formed a committee for Women's Suffrage which came to be known as the Conciliation Committee. The Conciliation Bill was drawn up with the object of granting the vote to about a million women house-holders. The Suffragettes called a truce during which they indulged only in propaganda. Between July and September, no less than four thousand meetings took place. By November, it became obvious that the Bill was being quietly side-tracked. A deputation of the W.S.P.U. went to the House and there was a violent scene during which the Prime Minister was showered with glass and one of his colleagues had his hat kicked to pieces by the infuriated women. From then on, the Suffragettes abandoned any attempt at moderation. A campaign of window-smashing was started. The windows of the big West End stores were shattered as were the windows of houses and offices belonging to those hostile to the cause. From the beginning of 1913, the policy of violence was stepped up to include fire-raising. Two churches were burnt down and Lloyd George's house was set on fire. Attempts were also made to cut pictures from their frames in the National Gallery. There were hundreds of arrests including most of the Suffragette leaders who promptly went on hunger strike. Forcible feeding having been discontinued, the Home Secretary tried to checkmate this move with the Prisoners' Temporary Discharge for Ill Health Bill. Prisoners released on licence under this bill "the famous Can and Mouse Bill", were sent to a house, nicknamed "Mouse Castle" by the Suffragettes and they were nursed back to health under police supervision. Time and again, many of them, including Annie Kenney, escaped in disguise and turned up at meetings to continue the struggle. In 1913, the cause acquired its first martyr in the person of Emily Davidson. Miss Davidson had just been released after serving a six months sentence for "firing a letter box". She went straight from prison to the Derby and stationed herself at Tattenham Corner with a Suffragette petition in her hand. As the King's horse came galloping up she rushed out and threw herself in front of it.

She died four days later from the injuries she received.

Throughout the year 1914, the Suffragettes kept up the pressure and in May of that year, they attempted to reach Buckingham Palace where they hoped to present a petition to the King. The attempt was foiled. In a way, it was the climax of the Suffragette Movement. The storm clouds were gathering over Europe and very soon the question of Votes for Women was swallowed up in the greater question of the deadly battle with Germany. The women who had chained themselves to railings now drove ambulances, made munitions, worked on farms, and took the places everywhere of the men who were fighting at the front. In the war, the women proved themselves when it ended, there was no longer any hostility to their demands, and the granting of their rights was merely a matter of time.

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HISTORY QUIZ, 1970

The winner of the Shield for the 1970 History Society Quiz is Hill House. Its team, consisting of D. Gilmour, G. McEwan, T. Scott and M. Berry, scored almost 30 points more than their nearest rivals and last year's winners, Palmer House.

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HEADLINES FROM HISTORY

Below are printed some fictitious headlines from events in the past as they might have been written by modern-day journalists.

MOSES, ON SINAI, GETS TEN-POINT PLAN

MARCO POLO TELLS RESULTS OF TRADE MISSION.

PHARAOH'S DAUGHTER EXPOSES "BABES IN BULLRUSHES"
RACKET

NESTON CONCUSSED IN ORCHARD DRAMA

BRAAVLEIS FOR RETURNING JUVENILE DELINQUENT

CANUTE DOWN WITH FLU AFTER BEACH FIASCO

BEN-HUR TO ENTER DRAG RACE

RED SEA PARTED - ALL SHIPPING RE-ROUTED.

DEATH EGYPTIAN STYLEA survey of the Ancient History of a Great Civilization

"A little damp trickle of life, that steals along undefeated, through the jaws of established death", these are the words the remarkable Rudyard Kipling employed to describe the sluggish River Nile. How true they are, for it was this "trickle of life" alone that fostered the Egyptian Civilization. "Egypt was the gift of the Nile", but how did this come about? The prevailing climatic conditions of the country today are a far cry from those of the wetter Paleolithic era, in which the Egyptians nomadic ancestors roamed. However, as the ice cap which then covered Europe began to retreat, North Africa started to dry up (as it were) This forced these barbaric wandering tribes to congregate in the fertile Nile Delta, later they spread along the Valley. Secure in the artificial environment from outside invasion- deserts surrounded them (to the south, east and west), while the sea formed the northern border - a multiplicity of isolated totemic clans arose, grouped in autonomous villages. Here in one of the most fertile areas of the world they prospered. Annually, following the inundation, when the Nile deposited a rich soil overlay on the low lying lands, their crops were sown. For a few weeks work they could in time reap a harvest that would more than satisfy their needs until the next flooding occurred. Unfortunately the Nile on occasions had a tendency to be erratic - this compelled man to exploit his natural gifts for organisation and inventiveness. Systemic irrigation was introduced and served to cancel out the "bad years". Thus the principles of civilisation were thrust on the embryonic Egyptian, earlier than on man in many other regions of the world.

Nevertheless to utilize this agricultural revolution to the greatest possible extent required an organised government. As the clans grew in numbers they strove for dominance, until ultimately, Menes (semi-legendary) leader of the Falcon (The God Horus) Clan conquered the Valley and the Delta tribes - uniting the groups into a simple state. Menes became the Pharaoh of the First Dynasty of Egypt. Thirty Dynasties were to follow from c 3200 to 332 BC. This eclipsed three-quarters of all recorded History..

Even before the unification of Egypt took place a basic religion had evolved. Fear is essential to human existence and as nature "enshrines within itself the twin aspects of good and evil" the forces of nature i.e. particularly the sun and the Nile, were designated spirits which eventually resulted in their personification.

In conjunction with the above, the pre-dynastic races noted that the hot, sterile desert sand to a certain extent preserved the corpses of the long buried. Did this lead them to speculate on the possibility of an after-life? If so they then embarked on a quest for immortality. For, this would explain why, in later burials, the bodies were placed on their left sides, the knees drawn up in a foetal position - awaiting rebirth? The "vainglorious" pyramids originated from the belief in "immortality".

Each village worshipped its own God - there was never a universal religion, only one common in external appearances. When the early settlement merged numerous Gods were incorporated into divine groups - triads. The following is an excellent example of this phenomenon; The cult of Osiris (in myths first pharaoh on earth, fertility god and ruler of the underworld) had spread peacefully throughout Egypt, by the time Menes, follower of Horus (symbol of majesty) and now ruler of the amalgamated country, established his capital at Memphis, close to the centre of veneration for the Sun god Re (King in heaven, regulator of season, bringer of light). Consequently it was not long before, Re, Osiris and Horus were inseparable godly relations.

Of course all this resulted in contradictory myths. The Egyptians, though, were tolerant and practical materialists, logic was seldom used and thoughts were never extended into theories. No attempt was made to arrange their theological system into "fixed truths" - after all why alter realities?

From the basic few gods, as centuries slid by new divinities were discovered or invented, until the number of gods, which totalled 2,000 plus, understandably reached unmanageable extents. Superstition had been introduced into every facet of life to awe the imagination and so hold together a fragmented nation with fears of unseen and in truth non-existent gods. Out of all this confusion over the complexities of the deities, one fact remained clearly impressed on the minds of these polytheists - the Pharaoh was the Gods representative on earth.

Perhaps the archetype of this god-king was the prehistoric rain-making chief, who was thought to control the health of his people. All the same he had come into being and was now regarded as visible and earthly embodiment of the supreme god. Thus god and monarch were one person - though this relationship was later to change. As the successor of the God Osiris, he was the exalted spiritual force that ruled over the forces of nature. If the rich soil was the gift of the gods, it was also indirectly that of the Pharaoh.

Made immortal (or so they thought) by magic rites, the king guaranteed by his own magic the fertility of the crops and flocks. By holding eminent domain over the whole land, The Pharaoh was entitled to a "tribute of offerings" (tax) and compulsory labour services from all its cultivators. Thus in the Old Kingdom (this period encompassed the third to tenth Dynasties: 2780 - 2100 BC) it was the Pharaohs and not the temples, who concentrated in their treasuries the surplus products of the land. This theocratic sovereign dominated every function of the centralised government. People owed allegiance to the god Pharaoh for had he not "devoured and digested" the "totem souls" of the clans? At first he alone worshipped the national gods on behalf of the nation. Yet his rule was not despotic, it was one of absolute government by popular consent, inspired by a common if somewhat disjointed faith. This gave the masses a psychological security and a national confidence which enabled them to defeat otherwise daunting obstacles. All the manifestations of culture in the Old Kingdom are henceforth concerned with the cult of the living and dead king - tremendous things were achieved by the populace for the sole benefit of their rulers. Can we today even comprehend the depth of feeling behind the usual verbal greeting of royalty-"life, health and strength be to you, good god Pharaoh"?

The credulity of the Pharaohs in their blind belief of life after death persuaded them to become pyramid builders. There is one point that must be stressed, the ancient Egyptians were not morbidly preoccupied with death - they had lost their fear of death, for, in the form of the desert it was never faraway. On the contrary they had enormous delight in nature and life. Ideally, the after-life was to be no more than prolongation of earthly pursuits in heaven. To be sustained in death, therefore, as one had been in life required food, liquids and a variety of the necessary household commodities, all of which were buried along side the departed. These basic principles of the death cult remained unchanged right up until foreign domination brought about the total collapse of their religion.

To trace the origin of the pyramids and the tombs in the Theban hills one has to return to the predynastic graves. At first they were simple oval pits, richly furnished with farming implements. The dead bodies were wrapped in cloth and hide and laid to rest in these sand pits. On learning the art of brick making, presumably from the Sumerians, the graves became brick-lined. The monumental style of building was ushered in during the Gerzean period (immediate pre-first Dynasty). As the clans of Egypt became unified a primitive class system appeared - there was now a marked contrast between the entombment of the rich and the poor. Due to

the social status of the wealthy a trench in the sand had grown instead into a huge excavation. To begin with the tombs were a rectangular grave dug in the sand. The walls were of brick, with a wooden ceiling supported by props. A mound of sand was placed on the top of this structure. These were the prototypes of the mastaba tombs of the Third Dynasty (2780 - 2720 B.C.) The early royal sepulchres of this type had a wooden burial compartment surrounded by offering-chambers and rooms for the bodies of the royal household. At one time there existed the gruesome custom of sacrificing (by burning alive) the court retinue on the death of the king along with broken weapons - they were interred in his tomb, so that he should not go unattended or unarmed into the spirit world. This system was replaced by use of the ushabti figurines - small dolls performing daily chores - which give us today the liveliest representation of the Egyptians domestic life. Densenti, fifth Pharaoh of the First Dynasty had his tomb paved with granite - the first instance of stone being used as a building material. By the time of Khasekheruci, ninth king of the second dynasty (1st and 2nd Dynasties c 3200 - 2700 B.C.) a Mastaba (Arabic word for bench) of tremendous size had developed, this was four cornered with oblique outer walls, it measured 223 feet long and 54 ft wide. It contained 58 separate apartments made of sun-dried brick grouped round a central burial chamber of stone - the oldest stone building known. The mastaba in shape generally resembled a house, the purpose of this being to stimulate early dwelling conditions for the dead man's spirits. Of these there were two. The Ka - the human's double and the Bai - the man's soul. As both were dependent on the cadaver for existence, every effort was made to preserve it from decay and desecration. When it came to the protection and preservation of the Pharaohs physical remains their efforts were doubled, so as to ensure the continuance of his magic work, on behalf of his people, from the other world. It is from this early period in Egyptian history that a primitive form of embalming was practised. During the Third and Fourth Dynasties, when large numbers of mastabas were constructed for the nobles, the tombs underwent considerable changes. The corpse was now buried in a small subterranean crypt, at the end of a deep shaft, carved out of the rock. The mud-brick structure above now became a solid mass of masonry, except for a offering chamber. Often the mummy chambers were decorated with pictorial presentations of the Egyptians way of life and some examples of hieroglyphic script can be found - eventually the archaeological record had merged into literary record. The contents of the mastaba proved the prevalence of expert craftsmen and extensive foreign trade. As the population and wealth grew, tombs became

proportionately larger, stronger and grander until the Egyptians suddenly launched themselves into the pyramid age.

The pyramid age was the "Golden age of the Old Kingdom". From out of the spring years of the Third Dynasty arose two of Egypt's first prominent personalities, King Djoser - a Pharaoh who needed a memorial tomb and his vizier Imhotep the author, priest, sage, magician and above all the adventurous architect who was to more than satisfy his master when he built it. The development of metal tools, particularly that of the copper saw with diamond edges, enabled the Egyptians to cut out of the mountainsides gigantic blocks of stone. With this advancement came the realisation that one could build on a large scale with stone. Imhotep achieved the fruition of this new conception with his stone and Step Pyramid - The first true pyramid. It consisted of six super imposed rectangular mastabas, with sloping sides, that diminished in size as they reached skywards. Nothing like it had been seen on earth before - it was a spontaneous creation, the style of which was copied by its successors. The Pyramid of Djoser was surrounded by erroneous stone chambers, government offices, courtyards and sacrificial temples. Djoser's predecessors brick mastaba to his magnificent monumental tomb had been an instantaneous step.

The so called "Bent Pyramid of Sneferu" first Pharaoh of the Fourth Dynasty (2615-2500 B.C.) was a further improvement on the step pyramid. One of the most interesting buildings in Egypt, this tomb was not stepped but straight-sided except for a curious change of angle in the middle.

In less than 100 years the God-Pharaoh worship had soared from the desert, from sand graves, from insignificant mastaba into miracle edifices. The fanaticism of the adoration of, what in the end turned out to be an ordinary human, had translated itself into stone when the ultimate peak was reached with the erection of the Great Pyramid of Giza.

The Son of Sneferu, Kheops, was determined to outdo his predecessors - in the end he did this to such an extent that it was not until the Nineteenth century A.D. 4,300 years later that a higher building was assembled in the world! Master builders in natural stone, the precision, remembering means available, achieved by the Egyptians in construction and fit has never been equalled. It is hard to comprehend the difficulties they experienced when we consider our technical advances - all they had for mechanical aids was the lever, rollers (the wheel had not yet come into

being) and the inclined plane to move 3.2 million cubic yards of stone, an estimated 2.3 million blocks of an average weight of 2½ tons each. The approximate cost of imitating this feat today, using their methods, would be £34 million plus. With unlimited sources of manpower the mausoleum took a task force of about 100,000 working in three month shifts, 20 years to complete, though out of this force probably only 4,000 skilled workers were regularly on the job. The remainder was made up of captives and the "neolithic" Egyptian cultivators - the simple people who worked under the dual encouragement gained from their religious devotion and the whip. Ironically they were excluded from the glories of the Old Kingdom. Limestone for the tomb facing was quarried on the East bank of the Nile, then had to be ferried across the river and hauled up to the site.

Construction was as follows: as the first layer of blocks was put down, long ramps (one from each corner) of stone and mud were built up to it. Up these ramps the blocks were dragged for the next course. When the top of the structure was capped the ramps were removed and the limestone facing laid. Finished it towered some 467 feet above the desert with a base length of 736 feet.

The power of organisation of the Pharaoh's government is well illustrated by the building of the Great Pyramid. By erecting pyramids the Pharaohs had no intention of becoming renowned or admired by posterity - they desired to live on in death, in greatness, undisturbed in an albeit false security. But why this pyramidal shape? Re, the Sun God, during the Third Dynasty, rose to ascendancy as supreme God of the Gods. The pyramid was meant to be a large scale reproduction of a sacred symbol to Re - notably that of the primeval hill that rose from the sea and on which Re created life. Alternatively it has been suggested they represented the "staircase to heaven". This geometric shape with a spiritual meaning had become obsolete by the time of the New Kingdom (1555 - 712 BC) although the Egyptians conservatism prevented them from discarding an ancient symbol even when its meaning was lost - the pyramid of the 18th Dynasty had shrunk to a mere 60 feet in height. Other groups of pyramids were built at Abusir and Saggara, though the previous grandiose style was now abandoned. The decrease in the size of the royal sepulchres coincides with a decline in status of the Pharaoh and Re. Egypt could not indefinitely support such an unproductive spending, as in the preparation for the king's future life - wealth dedicated to feed and cheer a corpse in a polished red granite sarcophagus. During the troubled Seventh to Tenth Dynasties all the

royal tombs were systematically violated by thieves. Grave robbery "oldest labour saving device" was rife.

Before discussing the Theban tombs of the New Kingdom one must briefly mention the history of the intervening years. Towards the end of the Old Kingdom a civil service had begun to appear. The governorships of the many districts of Egypt, which had been appointed to nobles by the Pharaoh alone, now became hereditary. Eventually this resulted in a decentralised government with various governors who regarded themselves as rulers of their own little principalities - they aimed at autonomy. The Old Kingdom dissolved into political and economic anarchy. Out of this "mess" emerged the Middle Kingdom (11th - 13th Dynasties 2100 - 1700 BC) Egypt's outlook now started to broaden but as yet no direct imperialistic ventures were attempted. A feudal monarchy had been established, though the Pharaoh never wielded the absolute power of the earlier centralised government. Political unity was recovered only once to be destroyed by vassal insubordination. Invaders of the country subjugated the Egyptians and set up their own form of government. This period was known as that of the Hyksos (14th c. 1700 - 1555 BC) 17th Dynasties. Ahmose, Theban founder of the New Kingdom expelled the Hyksos and replaced them with a centralised military monarch. Several professions, independent of royal tutelage, flourished and by so doing gave birth to a middle class. The peasants' lot improved for they were now allowed to sell goods on the open market. An awareness of the realities of human predicament led to the removal of the super-human attributes of the Pharaoh - he was now capable of vanity, greed, of being vulgar or good. His everyday habits, which up till then had remained sacrosanct, were revealed to the public for the first time.

Thebes, centre of worship of the gods, became more important than the devotion to Pharaoh who ruled as a human agent of the gods, his reign was often harsh and cruel. Nevertheless, it was an age of Imperialism, as Egypt conquered many of the neighbouring Asiatic kingdoms e.g. Assyria, Babylonia, who were forced to submit substantial tributary payments to the Pharaoh. Meanwhile the priests Amun gained in power and wealth during the prosperous Empire years, until the boundaries of what we now call politics and religion became ill-defined as the State church became one of the strongest institutions in the New Kingdom. Yet the church still owed its services to the Pharaoh for was he not the "Son of God"?

Immortality was open to all who could afford it. Embalming now became a fine art and distinct profession. Very simply the methods of embalming were as follows:-

a corpse of a rich person was eviscerated, purged internally, washed out and filled with aromatic substances and then soaked in natrum (to become desiccated) for seventy days. After this it was wrapped in bandages smeared with gum. The cheapest method of the above process, used for poor required that the intestines were cleaned out with a purge and the body placed in natrum for seventy days. As "rights for the masses, had meant rites for the masses" the Osiris cult grew. On the death the New Kingdom Egyptians had to face judgement, Osiris (through his priests) ceased promising resurrection by merely accepting the ritual and sacramental passports of the past. Thus moral codes had to be followed if one was to return to inhabit their earthly embalmed corpses (they never thoughts of who would unwind them) when, as they believed, Osiris would return to earth as eternal Pharaoh.

The futility of the plundered pyramids had long been realised, and the Pharaohs had taken to having secret tombs hewn out of the rock of the sun swent range of mountains, on the west bank of the Nile across from Thebes. These Theban Hills became the waste mausoleum for 70 generations of Egyptians over 2,000 years. No longer were the Pharaohs concealed only to be betrayed by "masses of masonry". In this great Necropolis there are basically two types of tombs; the communal catacombs for the mummies of the poor, and the deep galleries, offering appartments and sarcephagic chambers for nobles and officials. These rock tombs are a striking memorial to Egypt's imperial grandeur, golden face masks had ousted those of plaster. The walls were richly decorated, there appeared an unashamed delight in self-appraisal their materialistic gods favoured the wealthy, so chambers were crammed with funerary furniture and personal possessions. Despite concealed entrances, hidden staircases, false walls, massive grantie sacrophage all proved fruitless again the "hereditary skills" of the grave-robber. Divorced from high ideals, the respect for the dead, the fear of gods, even the might of Pharaoh, proved powerless when arrayed alongside mans lust for gold. As the Valley of the Kings was ransacked by thieves, the priests performed many secret re-burials of the Pharaohs to save them from these despicable treasure seekers.

With the coming to the Iron Age (1200 BC) came the slow decline and finally the collapse of Egypt. While harem intrigues and treachery undermined the authority of the Pharaoh, the countrv's territory was infiltrated by dufferebt races, Armed with iron weapons the barbarians could challenged and defeat the armies of a civilised state. First the Persians (525 -332 BC)

then the Greeks (332-30 BC) and finally the Romans (30 BC - 395 AD) occupied Egypt. Religious philosophies and cults of these nations, coupled with their bureaucratic form of governments aided further by the revolution of the science of reasoning, defeated the Egyptian priesthoods, broke their religion that revolved around the Pharaoh and submerged their policy of natural acceptance. A meditative poem written 4,000 years ago, today reveals to us the absurdity of their beliefs - "Nobody comes from the other world to tell us how he fared.... Make joyful holiday. Do not be said in life for see, nobody takes with him what he owns and nobody returns who has once departed". Egypt that had "caught a distant glimpse of the Promised land ended by wondering for centuries in the Wilderness".

by M. Davidson.

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HITLER AND THE JEWS

R.G. Addams

The full fury of "Nazi Race-hatred" was directed against the Jews whom, the Nazi alleged, were defiling the Aryan race. The Aryan or Nordic race was the "master race" with the rest of mankind being subordinate to them. The Germans asserted that they were Aryans, and destined to rule the world. The ideal Aryan's physical features were height, blond hair and beautiful figures.

The Jews were blamed for every misfortune that overtook or had overtaken Germany. Many Germans who were not members of the Nazi party were not sorry to see the Jews removed from the important jobs, which they held out of proportion to their numbers. Something like 50% of all the doctors and lawyers in Berlin and many university teachers were Jewish, as were the controllers of most of the larger newspapers.

The stupidity of the first boycott of Jews on April 1st, 1933, and the degrading anti-Semitic measures of the Hitlerite Government, made the name of National Socialism despised throughout the world and probably no other phase of Hitlerism has received such universal condemnation.

The Hitlerite Case concerning the Jews

Germany was in the unfortunate geographical position of being the first stage in the perennial westward push of the Jews - the "Ostjuden". The "Ostjuden" started from the Polish marches to move towards New York, and unless forced on, tended to stop in Berlin and Hamburg. Almost half of the Jews in Prussia congregated in Berlin and proceeded to obtain an unduly large share of the higher professional positions. The Jews showed no disposition to work on the land or at hand manual jobs.

But it was not this fact, so much as their undue hold on the professions, that annoyed the Germans.

In Berlin for example:-

- (a) 50.2% of the lawyers were Jews, and it was a truism that the barristers room in any Berlin Court was Jewish club.
- (b) In medicine 48% of the doctors were Jews, and it was said that their influence was greater than this, owing to their systematic seizure of the principal posts, especially in the hospitals.
- (c) More than two-thirds of the school and welfare doctors in Berlin were Jews.
- (d) Half of the teachers in the medical faculty in the University of Berlin were Jews.

While the Jews claimed that this predominance was due to their natural ability, the Aryans attributed it mostly to illicit Jewish combinations and influence

It was not only the numbers that perturbed Germany for, more serious in the German's eye, was the Jewish grip on culture and their influence on the minds and morals of the communities. The Germans believed that the Jews always flourished in times of national distress and thought that the events such as the Russian Revolution and the November Revolution (1918) in Berlin were happy hunting-grounds for the Lenins and Litvinous, the Rosa Luxemburgs and the Karl Liebknechts. They thought that the Magnus Hirschfeld Institute for Sexual Science and his writings about homosexuality and the Third Sex were examples of this direct attack on morals.

Most of the newspapers were in Jewish hands, these consisted of the Morgenpost, Vossische Zeitung, the Berliner Illustrierte Zeitung and the Berliner Tageblatt. The Germans once described the Jews as "a people with several vocal chords".

In some universities such as those in Breslau and Gottengen it was a drawback not to be a Jew. In 1914 a court established in Germany had Jews for 30% of the professors. But on a numerical basis 1% of the professors should have been Jews. These Jewish professors were particularly strong in the medical and philosophical faculties.

This first revolutionary government had ten Jewish members, while in Prussia, Jews were appointed to five ministries and to the leadership of the Press Bureau, the Food Ministry and the Educational Department.

The German Indictment of the Jews in Political Affairs

Nazi headquarters claimed that "8% of all the most important administrative posts in the Reich and in the provinces and communities were in the hands of the Jews until the death of Rathenau" and it particularly objected to the political activities of the Jewish vice-president of the Berlin City Police while Hitler claimed that Jewish groups financed the political movements of the left but he produced few facts in proof of this.

The German's greatest dislike of the Jews was caused by their connections with Communism. Hitler never referred to Communism without describing it as "Jewish Bolshevism" and his greatest claim was that he had saved Germany from Communist domination - in other words, Jewish hegemony.

"Juda Verneke" (Down with the Jews) was indeed Hitler's battle cry from the very beginning of his political career.

Hitlers Ideals on the Jews

Hitler had disliked the Jews for most of his life and anti-Semitism was the only clear idea he had when he founded the Nazi Party. Because of the fact of a Jewish minority securing an even large measure of professional success and due to racial influence, Hitler reached the position that "there can be no good Jew".

Hitler proceeded to condemn 6,000,000 human beings to a fate worse than death, irrespective of the individuals personal characteristics. His answer to the Jewish

problem was not brutality and blind punishment of women and children, but a removal of the conditions that were said to give the Jews an unfair advantage.

Hitler was not content with altering the real or fancied wrongs that the Germans had suffered at the hands of the Jews. He had to go on and exterminate the Jew's roots and branches in Germany.

The doctrine of "Blood and soil" became an increasingly virulent form of anti-Semitism, for it meant that he could never alter his attack on the Jews or else he would cut at the roots of his own philosophy.

The Attack on the Jews

The attack on the Jews began as soon as Hitler came to power. The so-called "Atrocity Campaign" in foreign newspapers against Hitler led to the official boycott of April 1st, 1933, organised by Julius Streicher.

Jew-baiting continued sporadically until the beginning of 1935, when it assumed a much more virulent form. Streicher began publishing a weekly newspaper called "Der Sturmer", which printed the most loathsome kind of propoganda against the Jews, for he realised that a mixture of pornography and low racial diatribe could be made to pay, and Nazi organisations saw to it that these newspapers were read by everybody, even the scholars in the schools.

The Nuremberg Congress (1933) was the climax of months of unrestrained brutality. Two laws were passed by the Reichstag on September 15th. The Nuremberg Laws relegated the Jews to a position of serfdom in Germany by asserting that "only a national of German or kindred blood can be a citizen of Germany". The Laws for the Protection of German Blood and German Honour, forbade marriage between Jews and Aryans and nullified marriage contracted (even abroad) in defiance of this law, it forbade extra-matril relationships between Jews and Aryans, stopped any Jew from employing female and domestic servants under forty-five years of age (later reduced to thirty-five years), forbade Jews to hoist national flags, and it provided penalties of penal servitude for breaches of its terms.

The Nazi Party's legal leader described these acts as "the first German charter of liberties for centuries" and said that "on them will depend in the future definitions of such terms as morality, order, decency, and public morals. They are the basis of liberty, the kernal of modern German justice."

As a result the Jews had no civil rights, for they were not citizens, could not vote or attend any political meetings, possessed no liberty of speech and could not sell books or antiques, could not receive aid from Winterhilfe organisations and if a Jew died in battle his name would not appear on memorials. This really deprived the Jews of the right to live in Germany and they were lucky if they could live unmolested by the Black Guards or Gestapo.

This was in effect a campaign of annihilation in the crudest form and was supported by every state instrument.

The campaign against the Jews was carried out in all walks of life and Germans gloried in their thoughts of the day when there would be no Jews in Germany. Shops were closed to Jews and signs were put up telling the Jews to keep out of the streets or villages. Such signs read "No Jews allowed in this village" or "Jews forbidden" or "Jews are not welcome here" or "Death to Jews here". Street stalls suddenly sprang up selling anti-Semitic literature, some of the cartoons were physically revolting and a collection of cuttings from "der Sturmer" or the Judenkenner have to be seen to be believed.

Moreover the Nazis did not restrict the problem only to its economic setting. They even thought that the cultural approach was too narrow and ended by having a wholesale attack on the Jews as a race. The fact that a man was a Jew rendered him unfit to be a member of any cultural society; for instance, one Jewish child could contaminate a whole school. Streicher even had a theory that if a woman once had a Jewish child, her blood would be so effected that all her later children would be Jews.

Hitler wrote in his autobiography, "Mein Kampf", that the true enemy of the world today was the Jew and that National Socialism must hold up for universal fury the wicked enemy of humanity as the true cause of all miseries".

Hitler also wrote in "Mein Kampf" that "the black-haired Jew-boy lurks for hours, his face set in satanic leer, waiting for the blissfully ignorant girl whom he defiles with his blood". What Hitler's main intention was, and he was nearly successful in doing so, was to rid Germany of all its Jews in the most diabolic attempt at genocide in history.

NELSON AND TRAFALGAR

D. Gilmour UVI

The Build up

Nelson, after many fruitless months chasing Villeneuve and the French fleet, returned a disappointed man to his country estate at Merton on August 20th, 1805 for a well-earned rest. He was, however, at home only 25 days before one Captain Henry Blackwood, fresh from sea, brought him the news that the French were abandoning their scheme of an attack across the Channel. This meant that Nelson's immediate duty was no longer in direct defence of his country; it was to destroy the French feet before it could slip away from Cadiz where Villeneuve had fled. With fantastic scenes of emotion, cheering and weeping, the people of London thronged to see off their hero, Lord Nelson, as on September 14 he went on board the "Victory". Commented Nelson "I had their huzzas before, I have their hearts now!"

On Sept. 15 the "Victory" weighed anchor at Spithead proceeding down the Channel in company with Blackwood's ship the 'Euryalus' the eyes of the fleet. On September 28, Nelson, relieving Vice-Admiral Collingwood, resumed command of the British fleet of Europe's south western coast. He transformed everything. Collingwood threw off the care which had begun to fatigue him and was glad to serve under a friend he respected. Their methods differed. Collingwood believed in a close watch, Nelson in a distant one. Collingwood's discipline was strict, while Nelson's was less so, but they trusted one another and were united in their purpose.

The fleet was made up of varied elements. Some ships were from Nelson's original squadron. Some had served with Calder in his action off Finisterre; some were newly joined from home. Such diverse material needed welding into a unit, and Nelson was the one man likely to do this quickly partly due to his personality and partly due to the great respect he commanded.

Nelson intended to stand well away into the Atlantic, leaving the business of observation to Blackwood and his frigates. Meanwhile, there was a master plan to explain to the captains. This was issued as a formal memorandum to each commanding officer, but Nelson expounded it in person to his men. His objective was to pierce the line of the combined French and Spanish fleets in two or three places by sailing directly at it rather than by cruising down alongside it. Although this meant that the leading British ships would be exposed to the full power of the enemy's broadsides without being able to bring their own guns to bear Nelson

felt that it would "surprise and confound the enemy... it will bring forward a pell-mell battle, and that is what I want". The effect of this plan on his officers promoted Nelson to write in his diary, "Some shed tears but all approved. It was new, it was singular, it was simple". It was no wonder that Nelson described his reception in the fleet as "causing the sweetest sensation of my life".

Many of the officers did not believe that Villeneuve would dare to venture out of Cadiz, for the season was growing late and he could stay safely the whole winter. Nelson, however, thought differently and Napoleon played straight into his hands, first by ordering Villeneuve into the Mediterranean at the earliest opportunity, and then by sending a senior admiral to relieve him. The insult was too much for Villeneuve to bear - he had to retrieve his reputation by fighting. On October 19, after Nelson had been given a few essential weeks to shape his fleet, Blackwood reported that the French and the Spaniards were preparing to sail.

Villeneuve had in fact ordered part of his force to drive Blackwood away, together with the other inshore British ships. The scheme had failed, but since the ships concerned in that operation could not return to Cadiz because of an offshore wind, Villeneuve had no choice but to sail out with his entire force. He was willing to be bold because he believed that Nelson had detached a number of ships to provision at Gibraltar, and also because he knew that in any case he had but a few days longer in which to exercise command. But Villeneuve had overestimated the number of British ships provisioning at Gibraltar for Nelson still had 27 of the line with him against Villeneuve's thirty-three of which 15 were Spanish.

When Nelson had news that the enemy was stirring, he was well out to sea. He ordered his ships to steer at once for the Strait of Gibraltar, intending to deny the enemy passage into the Mediterranean. The night of October 19 and the day and night of the 20th, were taken up with manoeuvres on both sides. Villeneuve was struggling, not with entire success, to get his ships into regular formation, while Nelson, on the other hand, kept his main striking force out of sight long enough to ensure that his opponent would be fully committed to the plan of carrying out his orders by sailing through the Strait. At first light on October 21, the fleets sighted each other, just off the coast of Spain's Cape Trafalgar. Nelson signalled for his ships to dispose themselves into two columns, according to his plan; the windward under his own command, the leeward under Collingwood. Such wind as there was blew towards the enemy as Nelson would have hoped.

At about 8 o'clock or a little earlier Villeneuve reversed course, an action anticipated by Nelson - his purpose was to retreat upon Cadiz. As it was now impossible for the French and the Spaniards to reach Gibraltar without a major battle, the move was sound. Whatever the result of the fight with Nelson, which was not unavoidable, Villeneuve could at least repair his damage afterwards.

Although the wind was light, there was a swell from the west which gave Nelson the idea - justified by events - that there would be a gale before night-fall. The advance towards the enemy was slow, never more than walking pace, though every ship crowded on sail. There was much to say and do and time to do it in. One of Nelson's first acts was to summon the frigate captains aboard the 'Victory' to give them final instructions. These amounted to no more than that they were to tell succeeding ships to get into action as best they could, without regard to any regular order of sailing. Captain Blackwood and Nelson's greatest friend Hardy were called to his day cabin to witness a codicil to his will in which he entrusted Emma Hamilton to the care of his country (a clause ignored after his death). Later he withdrew to his quarters where Pasco the signal lieutenant found him writing a prayer which was found after the battle and which has passed into the Treasury of the English language. It shows the completely unselfish and patriotic nature of Nelson's character.

"May the great God, whom I worship, grant to my country, and for the benefit of Europe in general, a great and glorious victory; and may no misconduct in anyone turnish it..... To Him I resign myself and the just cause which is entrusted to me to defend. Amen. Amen. Amen."

When Nelson returned to the upper deck he said to his signal lieutenant "Mr. Pasco, I wish to say to the fleet "England confides that every man will do his duty". Pasco then asked if he could substitute "expects" for "Confides" because the former was the first word in the signal book and "confides" would have to be spelled out. Nelson replied with seeming satisfaction, "That will do, Pasco, make it directly". Thus it was that the ships went into action with the now famous signal flying from the halyards of the 'Victory' with bands playing and sailors cheering until action was joined. There were those in the fleet who thought the message superfluous. Collingwood for example, but when Napoleon heard of it later, he ordered a similar message to be painted on all his ships of war. By this simple action, Nelson gave his men the fillip needed just before battle and it shows just how great was this man's understanding of and loyalty to his sailors.

The Battle.

Nelson was taking a grave personal risk in order to get quickly into action, for it was against all reason and precedent that the 'Victory' should lead her line, particularly in an action where the foremost ships were bound to suffer heavily because they were approaching the enemy bows-on and would be unable to bring their broadsides to bear until they had closed. Blackwood, Hardy and other senior officers were so concerned for Nelson's safety that at one time they actually persuaded him to let the second ship the 'Temeraire' overtake the 'Victory'. But when the moment came, Nelson changed his mind and ordered his captain to keep her in station astern.

Unconcerned for himself, Nelson grew agitated when Collingwood in the 'Royal Sovereign' leading his own line was seen to be exposing himself in exactly the same way. Nelson actually signalled to one of the 74-gun ships to overtake the admiral and get into action before him. But Collingwood was as obstinate as Nelson and continued to crowd on sail, thus remaining far ahead of the rest of his column. Collingwood got into action about noon, fighting alone for some time until succeeding ships could bring him support.

Nelson's column did not get into action until about half an hour after Collingwood's and in doing so the 'Victory' sustained 'such a fire as had scarcely before been directed at a single ship' without being able to bring her own guns to bear in reply. For the rest of that crowded October day every vessel became involved in the "pell-mell" battle which Nelson had brought about.

The struggle was fierce and costly particularly among the leading British ships (the 'Victory' had to be towed back to Gibraltar) but when the day closed, at least 18 Frenchmen and Spaniards had struck their colours though not all of them had actually been boarded and secured. - the final figures showed 29 enemy ships virtually destroyed; there were no British ships lost.

The way of attack was, in effect, the Battle of the Nile in reverse. There, the French rear was made impotent because it could not join the action; at Trafalgar, the leading enemy ships were excluded. In the conditions of the day it took a long time to turn, and by the time the leading ships could join they were to last.

The most unorthodox sea victory of the age of sail had been won in the space of about 4 hours and Nelson

had achieved his wish. As a fleet Villeneuve's combined force had been broken beyond recovery and only the gale, which Nelson had foreseen, and the havoc it wrought had robbed the victors of all but four of their prizes, and Villeneuve, together with his entire staff became a prisoner of war. Napoleon never forgave his admiral, who died, in disgrace, within a few months of the action. But before the battle ended in triumph, for the British, tragedy struck.

About 1.35 p.m. as he was pacing around the quarter deck with Hardy, Nelson was shot by a marksman in the French 'Redoubtable' a ship which was splendidly handled by Lucas, her captain. "They have done for me at last, Hardy", cried Nelson as he fell. "My backbone is shot through". He was carried below by a sergeant of marines and a party of seaman, his face covered by a handkerchief so that the men should not be discouraged by the sight of their wounded admiral.

Nelson lingered for 3 hours in great pain but he lived to hear from Hardy the news he longed for, greeting it with a new famous words "God be praised I have done my duty". He died soon after begging up to the time of death that Lady Hamilton and his daughter Horatia be well looked after. Having bade farewell to his great friend Hardy - "Kiss me Hardy" he said, Nelson died content at the time of his supreme fulfillment. Of the many records of his death none in its own way is more characteristic and complete than the formal words entered in the flagships log;

"Partial firing continued until 4.30 when a victory having been reported to the Right Honourable Lord Viscount Nelson, K.B, and Commander-in-Chief, he then died of his wound". His country came first always. Between them, his admirals had set a standard for all time, not only of tactics but of personal conduct, and every circumstance had conspired to make the day one of the most dramatic in naval annals.

What then of Nelson himself? His life was given to a single end: that of making his country great by means of her navy, and in this aim he undoubtedly succeeded. But this material achievement is not why Nelson gained fame. He was a man to command love, able to inspire every one around him to excel themselves, a genius in leadership, a man whose state funeral has only been surpassed by that of Winston Churchill, as regards the emotions exhibited. Even today the mere word "Nelson" incites to higher levels the seaman of Britain and it is perhaps only fitting that this hero should have been killed on the scene of his greatest, most daring victory - Trafalgar.

OPERATION BARBAROSSA

M. Berry 3A

On 22nd June 1941, Hitler launched "Operation Barbarossa" - his invasion of Russia. The order to attack was given by Hitler himself because first, he was opposed to Communism and secondly, Russia was to supply Germany with food and oil. Hitler wanted those supplies urgently. Germany was also to find its "breathing or living space" in the East.

From the start Hitler underestimated Russian strength and although the war started brilliantly for the Germans they fell victim to the same things which defeated Napoleon - THE WINTER - and the Russian "scorched earth" policy. In a rapid six-month advance however, the German armies were hammering at the Gates of Leningrad and Moscow. The Russian armies were not destroyed and Partisan groups harassed German Communications behind their lines.

By now, the bitterest fighting was taking place on the front. Hitler had been unable to enter Leningrad or Moscow-because he restrained his tanks from entering when there was no opposition - and the Russians even forced the Germans back a little. The Germans rallied however, and May 1942, were at the gates of Stalingrad. They entered the city in September. This battle was the historic turning point of the Campaign.

Stalingrad was occupied by General Paulus' 6th Army, Army Group B, the 32nd Motorised Infantry Division, Panzer Corps H and other minor units. When Stalingrad finally was surrounded, General Manstein ordered Paulus to move back through the Myshkova through the "Pocket". Paulus however, was unwilling as retreating was not Germanlike and anyway, Hitler ordered against it. If Paulus had been satisfied Stalingrad could not be held he would have been justified in disobeying Hitler's order, but he argued it could be held and said he would not start towards the Donskaya River. Above all, he said, he would need the fuel for his tanks.

For a full week, the fourth Panzer Army's troops held on to the Myshkova Bridgehead, but they waited in vain for the promised attack which would take off the pressure. The Russians however, counterattacked on all fronts ensuing moving of troops and so weakening the Myshkove Bridgehead. The Russians doubled attacks on this link and on December 27th 1942 they forced the Germans across the Askai.

Nevertheless, Manstein refused to change his belief that the arrival of three Divisions from Army Group 4 and 1500 tons of fuel and food flown to the sixth army of Stalingrad would help stave off the Russians. The first surrender call by the Russians went to Paulus on January 8th. Paulus considered with the 4th Panzer Army fighting 50 miles behind Russian lines he thought more, but when the news came through from Hitler, "The sixth army will fight on" he refused the terms. The sixth army was then split up into three groups in Stalingrad and 18,000 wounded Germans were left without medical care. 30,000 had previously been flown out.

Paulus reported that he had lost touch with more than 2/3 of his army on January 24th, but sent a message ordering a break out to the south-west by organised troops; a few did make it, hoping to help the 4th Panzer army and reach Army Group A at the Kalnuk steppes.

On January the 30th the Russians broke into the inner ring in Stalingrad from the west and north-west. The Germans in these areas surrendered because they had no ammunition or did not want to draw fire to wounded comrades. Resistance soon ceased in the two southern resistance pockets.

On January 31st, Paulus, now a Field-Marshal and on the verge of a nervous collapse surrendered with his aides.

The northern resistance pocket held until February 2nd when the remnants of six divisions - 240,000 men - laid down their arms. The Battle for Stalingrad was over.

The tide had turned. The Russian advance continued through the summer of 1943 and when winter came they had reached the Dniener and re-occupied Kiev. The Crimea was recovered in 1944 and with the Normandy landings, the Germans were finally driven out of Russian soil.

The failure of the Russian campaign was caused by three main reasons. First, the failure to drive the Allies out of Greece and Crete in 6 weeks instead of the allotted one week. This meant the Germans were out of schedule for winter quarters in Russia. Secondly, the Gestapo stepping in the Ukraine after the army (Wehrmacht) had got the support of the people and the oil and wheat. The most important reason for the failure was the winter climate which caught the Germans outside the cities (they were supposed to be in for winter), without any winter clothing.

ROME - ITS RISE AND FALL

G. Morgan. C2

Rome, which was destined to unite the ancient world in one great empire with a common culture, showed no early promise of greatness. Despite the fact that the Italian peninsular was relatively populous, the site of Rome was uninhabited before the first millennium B.C. because of volcanic activity. The rest of the Italian peninsular was inhabited by invading tribes from the north. These people lived on the hills and plains. Along the mountain backbone from north to the south were the Italic tribes; the plains south of the R. Tiber were settled by Latins and still other tribes, Ligurians and Deseti in the north and Messapi and Siculi in the south have left scanty evidence of their existence. Two foreign peoples brought a higher civilisation to Italy before 700 B.C. The Greeks established colonies in South Italy and Sicily called "Magra Graecia" after them and north of the Tiber was the realm of the non-Indo-European speaking Etruscans whose power eventually extended from the Po Valley to south of Naples. Little is known of their origin but they may have come from Asia Minor and have even thought to have been indigenous.

Rome originated as a series of villages built on hills and occupied by shepherds and farmers of the Latin tribe and the Sabines. Eventually these two tribes and their villages united. The marsh which had been a cemetery for the shepherds was drained and became a civic and business centre dominated by the Capitoline Hill - the Forum. Roman tradition attributed the foundation and union to Romulus and dated it in 753 and told of six succeeding kings, 3 of whom were Latin or Sabine and 3 Etrusean. The development of the united city and its protective earthworks should be attributed to the Etrusean period. The second last King, Serius Tullius strengthened his army and reorganised the citizens according to wealth. The last king was expelled from Rome under circumstances which made the title of Rex or king forever hateful to Romans. This period of history marked great progress for Rome, as it had the advantage of learning the ways of the far advanced Greek civilisation under Etrusean rule and although the last king was expelled, Etrusean influence on religious and political forms in Rome remained great and permanent.

Rome inherited from the regal period a number of basic social and political concepts which were very important. Perhaps the most important institution was the close family groups and the supreme power of the father over both persons and property within the family. This is essential if any state is to remain strong and

united as it is the parents who bring up the future citizen and their control over their children keeps them from becoming abnormal. The people themselves fell into two groups known as orders: the patricians and the plebians or plebs. The plebs were citizens serving in the army and voted, but in the early republic were debarred from office. The patricians were a group of leading families from whose members the Senate was drawn. This was a council of elders which was appointed and consulted regularly on public questions. In spite of the fact that development was largely hindered during the regal period the sound structure within Rome and its system of laws and government created by the kings as well as the very efficient army and its system of registration made it a powerfully united unit to be launched against the scattered tribes around.

After the expulsion of kings in 509 B.C. authority was transferred to magistrates called consuls. This system eliminated neglect of the affairs of the Republic because of selfish desires of the individual by having two consuls to keep each other in check and by limiting their power by the short term of office. In 493 B.C. the plebs used their importance to the army to agitate for better positions, the military secession of the plebs led to the establishment of tribunes which increased in number and whose veto was valid against all but the highest laws. Because of further agitation by the plebs the law was modified and posted in the Forum for all to read. After expulsion of the kings there had been wars with the neighbouring Latins. These wars ceased in 493 B.C. when Rome and the Latin League made an offensive and defensive alliance. Together they agreed to keep the invaders from the north divided. However the tables were turned in the second half of 400 B.C. When the long and bitter struggle with the Etrusean City of Deid ended with the destruction of the city by the Romans, Rome became the largest and strongest city in central Italy. A sudden reversal of Roman fortunes damaged its strength and prestige for a generation. The Italian peninsular was overrun by a great invasion from the north by the Gauls. Rome was nearly defeated but the citadel on the Cytoline Hill held out and after 387 B.C. the Gauls finally withdrew to the Po Valley. This invasion rid the Romans of their enemies, the Etruseans, and initiated drastic reforms in army and civil service.

Rome recovered after about forty years and expanded by a system of alliance which attached tribes to the city. By 298 B.C. most of the tribes around Rome were either defeated or won over. There was a conflict with the Greeks which ended in the defeat of the latter. This war brought Rome recognition as a major military power.

and left her open to a flood of new Greek ideas and hence there was much cultural development in Rome. Rome became a Mediterranean power by 265 B.C. and this brought her into conflict with the great sea port of Carthage. This was a vital stage in Roman history. The first Punic War which lasted 23 years forced Rome to become a naval power and caused her great losses. A Gallic invasion led Rome to undertake the conquest of the Po Valley to end the Gallic menace. The Second Punic wars brought Roman armies into conflict with Carthage's greatest general Hannibal. By delaying tactics and the brilliance of Deipio at Zama, Hannibal was defeated in 202 B.C. Within a year Rome became involved with Maceon. Philip V was defeated and Greek freedom established. Rome expanded in the west and in 146 B.C. Carthage was utterly destroyed and its occupants sold into slavery. In Rome great families were linked together by intermarriage and the growth of large estates led to the influx of small farmers to Rome. Thousands of slaves from many wars had to be cared for and moralists warned of the decline of ancient morals caused by new wealth, luxury and foreign ways.

During the Roman revolution of 133 B.C. more great reforms were made. During this period Pompey, a brilliant general appeared and he cleared the Mediterranean of pirates and won victories against Roman enemies. He enlarged the Roman frontiers to the Euphrates. Generally, he increased Rome's strength tremendously. Another powerful general, Caesar, emerged and civil war followed. Pompey soon lost power and was killed. Caesar was a brilliant soldier and politician but he was assassinated by his own friends in 44 B.C. The civil war carried on until all the conspirators were killed or defeated by Octavian, the future Augustus. With the death of Caesar, the Republic ended and the empire began. Augustus was the first and greatest emperor, so great that he was worshipped as a god by the Romans. He turned Rome "from a city of brick into a city of marble". The soldier emperor, Trojan, pushed the boundaries of the empire to their furthest extent in the second century A.D.

The emperors ruled the empire from 27 B.C. to A.D. 476. In all there were 86 of them. Out of this 86, 33 were assassinated, 5 committed suicide and 14 were killed in battle with barbarians. Most of them took advantage of imperial powers and were tyrannical. Caligula, probably the worst tyrant, used to torment his soldiers. For example, there are records of such deeds: at night when some soldiers were on guard duty the emperor had to give the captain of the guard a pass word and the captain would pass this on to his men. Caligula on one occasion gave the undignified pass word "lady parts". One can imagine the captain delivery this pass in the most dignified manner possible

and the humiliation he must have felt. Most of the Emperors did little for the Roman cause and all they could for personal glory and luxury. In A.D. 398 the first blow came to the unity of the empire when it was divided into two, the west and the east. In 492 B.C. the last Emperor Romulus Augustulus was deposed by a barbarian captain Odoacer in the West. The east survived great hardships and became the Byzantine Empire.

One of the most puzzling questions which confront historians is why a power which lasted over a thousand years and which controlled most of the known ancient world should collapse? No other power has ever lasted this long and it is doubtful whether any will. The usual reaction of anyone confronted with this question is to say "the barbarians". People forget that from the very dawn of their existence the Romans had barbarian problems. They surely hastened the inevitable. The causes, though complex, can be divided into four and summarised into: the eastward expansion of the empire, the decline of the economy, barbarian invasion and the decline of the social structure. Hadrian's refusal to extend the empire ended an important source of resources and labour. He realised that the empire was becoming too huge to manage. Though slavery was declining, the economy did not improve its technology and develop in depth for a mass market while the development of the provinces coincided with the decline in Italy. Even so, the balance might have continued long but for two unforeseeable factors - depopulation caused by the Great Plague in 160 A.D. and devastation wrought by the barbarians invaders. As a result, the urban middle class was weakened and the poor depressed even further. Barbarians dominated the army. The east probably survived because it kept better control of soldiers and landowners and because the barbarians were diverted to the west at the critical moment. Also there remained in the east reserves of manpower and industry of less impaired by invasion. The west had no protected centre. In a sense, the Empire had failed when it had to sacrifice its citizen for the survival of the state.

Probably the most effective and disastrous cause was the decline of the social structure of the empire. This cause can be subdivided into: the breakdown of the family and the rapid increase of divorce, the spiralling rise of cases and extravagant spending, the mounting craze for pleasure and brutal sports, the expanding production of armaments to combat ever-increasing threats of enemy attacks, when the real enemy was the decay of the society from within and the decay

of religion into myriads and confusing forms, leaving the people without a guide.

The parents shape the future citizens of a state and they are the only ones who can control their children properly. Once the state interferes then confusion and rise in crime and divorce is bound to result, because the men and women have had an inadequate family education and have been allowed to go against their parents. In spite of the criticisms of religion it is very necessary if any state is to survive because as every person thinks differently and has different ideas to those of other people, there must be something to bring people together under one issue: religion serves this purpose. Because the government became so complex and confusing that no ordinary man could understand it, the common people became uninterested in their government and as a result unity in the empire declined as the majority of the people did not know what they were living for and how the country was being run. People now turned to pleasure and this became a more important part of their lives, the happiness of Rome appeared to hang on the event of a race and the free workmen's demand for short hours and high wages grew great. (To encourage industry in her various satellite nations, Rome attempted a policy of unrestricted trade, but the Roman working man was unable to compete with the cheap foreign labour and demanded high tariffs).

The Roman Empire and the Roman order of things were considered indestructible, eternal.... And so in this dream of the absolute fixity of the Roman system, men went on building up riches, studying, enjoying themselves, dissipating - doing everything except preparing for war... and so the barbarians at length destroyed a society that was more slowly destroying itself.... Their fall was great, while the lesson of their fall lies patent to the twentieth century.

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FILM CRITIQUES

During the course of the year the History Society showed several films of historic value, the critiques of which follow below. Attendance at these films was open to the entire school and in addition Marymount College and the Girl's High had standing open invitations to attend the showings. The result was that fairly large numbers attended each film-showing and consequently the Society was able to break even money-wise, and on some occasions show a profit.

The showing of films by the Society was an innovation and we hope that this precedent is continued in the future.

"BECKET"

While this evening must rate as one of the most successful as regards attendance, it was by far the most disappointing in outcome. However, the fact that the sound became non-existent three-quarters of the way through, and the film had a nasty habit of "jumping" now and then, must not detract from what promised to be a very good show.

Peter O'Toole as Henry II and Richard Burton as Becket are both well-known actors in their own rights and as the "leads" gave thoroughly convincing performances. The tale of Thomas a Becket murdered in Canterbury Cathedral being well-known, the success of the film lay in the dialogue and it was to the actors credits that they held the audience as they did, despite a few jarring anachronisms.

The Historical value of the film was great, interesting and revealing insights of the times being achieved. From the evidence of the film, wenching seemed to be the main occupation of the upper classes, and in particular Henry II, who seemed singularly pre-occupied with sex. This aside, the amazing and profound faith of Becket was excellently brought out, and it was most unfortunate that the climax of the story namely, the murder of Becket and repentance of Henry, was not seen, for these two events illustrate both the victory of Church over State and the depth of Becket's faith.

In conclusion, then, I must re-iterate that this was a film that promised much, and a film greatly worth seeing in its entirety.

D.G.

"THE AGONY AND THE ECSTASY"

The Society showed "The Agony and the Ecstasy" on Wednesday 20th May and it was well attended by pupils from U.B.H.S. and U.G.H.S. This "epic" on the life of Michaelangelo was adapted from Irving Stones mammoth biography of the same name. It starred Charlton Heston as Michaelangelo and Rex Harrison as Pope Julius II. The film concentrated almost entirely on the painting of the Sistine Chapel and succeeded in portraying the rather strong personal relationship between Julius

and Michaelangelo. It successfully indicates that it was only under protest that Michaelangelo agreed to paint the mural decorations for the ceiling of the Chapel. He would much rather have been working on the building of the great memorial tomb for Julius II. He had constantly to be bullied and even threatened by Julius.

Michaelangelo's work on the ceiling of the Sistine Chapel has been hailed as the greatest series of minor paintings the world has ever seen and it is thus a tribute to the photography of the film that it manages to convey the brilliance of the painting.

There were several glowing inaccuracies but these must not allow us to detract from the considerable value of the film. This period in history is not studied by any classes in the school and thus the film must be considered of great use in stimulating a wider interest in history.

"MARIE ANTOINETTE"

This film from a historical point of view was quite beneficial, in the setting out of the people of Paris, and the extravagancies of the court life at the time. The Revolutionary atmosphere was well shown in the short time. There was one chief criticism in that the main characters, namely Louis XVI and Marie Antoinette were over sentimentalised, they were in such a pitiful state at times that one tended to laugh at them instead of pity them, as should have been the case. The character's were also rather distorted to appeal to the audience from an entertainment point of view. This was especially the cause with Louis XVI.

Still the film proved quite informative to people studying that period and time in history and to others it proved quite entertaining.

T.S.

"RASPUTIN"

Rasputin, the Mad Monk, was a film much enjoyed by all. However, in being a horror film the character of Rasputin was so distorted that it was hard to believe he performed some of his actions in real life. Again the background to the film was of historical value, and the film was primarily based on historical fact. Perhaps the most important part that is, his dominating

influence in politics was greatly looked over, especially his domination of the Empire and state affairs. The film tended to dwell too much on his spiritual powers and on his many love affairs, and it was wrongly thought this he met his death, which in itself is a contrast to historical fact.

The film, being the typical horror and sadistic one, was very entertaining and one would have hoped that it could have been made to be of more accurate, historical interest.

T.S.

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The Editor would like to thank Mrs. Barnes without whom this magazine would not have been a reality. Thanks also to the Printing Club for the valuable work done in printing the covers.

No letters for publication were received by the editor and he would like to remind readers that letters or correspondence of any kind, including those with criticisms or suggestions for Zuro, are more than welcome.

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